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Integration of heterogeneous Data and Evidence towards Regulatory and HTA Acceptance

WP6 Policy recommendations to enable HTA decision making

D6.3 Consensus policy recommendations for data-sharing, access and use governance policies

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Executive Summary

IDERHA has identified 10 thematic areas where further targeted policy recommendations could be developed to better support health data-sharing, access, and use, particularly in regard to developing trust and transparency in these processes:

- Thematic Area 1: Aligning national and EU-wide legal frameworks and establish common interpretations and standards
- Thematic Area 2: Improving data management and access procedures
- Thematic Area 3: Engaging with the public and promoting health and data literacy to enhance trust in data-sharing initiatives
- Thematic Area 4: Establishing and maintaining high data security measures
- Thematic Area 5: Following an ethical framework for data-sharing and use
- Thematic Area 6: Improving semantic interoperability
- Thematic Area 7: Allocating enough resources for the implementation and sustainability of data-sharing initiatives
- Thematic Area 8: Creating standardized incentives for data-sharing
- Thematic Area 9: Exploring consent mechanisms
- Thematic Area 10: Establishing a network for data-sharing initiatives to leverage alignment and synergies

These thematic areas were formed through consultation with a number of different types of stakeholders including patients, patient advocates, diversity and inclusion advocates, Data Protection Officers (DPOs), Information Governance Officers and representatives from established

data-sharing initiatives. They also take into account and build on the work of other recommendations already created in this area, for example the reports of TEHDAS 1, as well as insights generated in other IDERHA work packages and tasks.

Moving forward, IDERHA task 6.3 aims to build on this foundational work by conducting a public consultation in early 2025. This consultation will:

- Determine which thematic areas should be taken forward to further expand and refine the recommendations within it
- Determine if there are any other key thematic areas that are felt to be of high priority that should be considered
- Seek input on the feasibility and priority of individual recommendations, including areas for further exploration, target audiences and implementation considerations
- Understand how we can go beyond what has already been recommended by other initiatives

D6.3 Consensus policy recommendations for data-sharing, access and use governance policies 1

Document History.....	3
Executive Summary	3
Abbreviations.....	6
Context	7
Current state of existing policy recommendations for data access and use for secondary purposes 10	
Methods.....	19
Results.....	22
Thematic Area 1: Aligning national and EU-wide legal frameworks and establish common interpretations and standards.....	23
Thematic Area 2: Improving data management and access procedures	25
Thematic Area 3: Engaging with the public and promoting health and data literacy to enhance trust in data-sharing initiatives	27
Thematic Area 4: Establishing and maintaining high data security measures	29
Thematic Area 5: Following an ethical framework for data-sharing and use	31
Thematic Area 6: Improving semantic interoperability	33
Thematic Area 7: Allocating enough resources for the implementation and sustainability of data- sharing initiatives	35
Thematic Area 8: Creating standardized incentives for data-sharing	37
Thematic Area 9: Exploring consent mechanisms	38
Thematic Area 10: Establishing a network for data-sharing initiatives to leverage alignment and synergies.....	39
Discussion.....	40
Strengths and Limitations.....	40
Other thematic areas	41
Next steps.....	42
References.....	43
Appendix	45
IDERHA Task 6.3 Patient workshop 14/09/2023 - Full report.....	45
IDERHA Task 6.3 Data stakeholder workshop 31/10/2023 - Full report	53
IDERHA Task 6.3 Data providers workshop 20/06/2024 - Full report.....	64
IDERHA Task 6.3 and Task 6.2 Patient Organizations and Diversity and Inclusion Advocates Workshop 01/10/2024 - Full draft report	74

AI	Artificial Intelligence
DQF	Data Quality Framework
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EHR	Electronic Health Record
EIRA	European Interoperability Reference Architecture
EIT	European Institute of Innovation and Technology
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2O	Health Outcomes Observatory
HCP	Healthcare Professional
HTA	Health Technology Assessment
IDAGC	Integrated Data Access Governance Council
IDERHA	Integration of Heterogenous Data and Evidence for Regulatory and HTA Acceptance
RWD	Real-world data
RWE	Real-world evidence
TEHDAS	Joint Action Towards European Health Data Space

Context

The IDERHA (Integration of Heterogeneous Data and Evidence towards Regulatory and HTA Acceptance) project, launched in 2023, aims to facilitate the secure and streamlined access and secondary use of diverse health data, such as electronic health records (EHR), computed tomography images and health data from wearable devices.

The goal of **Work Package 6** within IDERHA is to reach a consensus on feasible policy recommendations for facilitating research, innovation, as well as regulatory and Health Technology Assessment (HTA) decision-making by combining and utilizing diverse health data. The recommendations will concentrate on the larger policy context and aim to **(1) identify policy gaps and best practices** for high-quality heterogeneous health data for research and innovation; **(2) accelerate policy development for the use of real world data (RWD) and real world evidence (RWE)** in regulatory and HTA decisions for medicines and medical technologies and **(3) create multi-stakeholder agreement** on governance guidelines for proper data access and utilization.

Task 6.3 within Work Package 6 is specifically focused on developing consensus policy recommendations to support the aim of **creating multi-stakeholder agreement on governance guidelines for proper data access and utilization**. This report, **Deliverable 6.3**, is the first report from this task, outlining the preliminary thematic areas regarding data access, data use and governance policies in which we believe consensus recommendations are required. The recommendations in this report are intentionally high-level, as further consultation is needed to develop granularity and specificity.

As this deliverable is the first of a series of reports, it will be updated and added to in an iterative process as public consultation and further stakeholder engagement workshops take place. A further draft recommendations paper will be published in November 2025, with the final recommendations due to be published in March 2027. The thematic areas and recommendations in this report should therefore be considered draft, with the expectation that over time they will be refined and, where necessary, be made more explicit and detailed to ensure actionability.

For the development of this report, we have conducted various exploratory workshops with different key stakeholders, such as patients and patient representatives, inclusion and diversity advocates, academia, industry, and Data Protection Officers (DPOs). The aim of the workshops was to hear directly from stakeholders on the current challenges they see for successful heterogeneous health data access and utilization for secondary purposes. It was also to understand their initial thoughts on solutions to these challenges. However, exploring specific solutions to current challenges will be the primary aim of the later phases of this work.

The thematic areas and recommendations in this report have been developed:

1. In-parallel with Work Package 6 Task 6.2 which has the aim of **identifying policy gaps and best practices** for high-quality heterogeneous health data for research and innovation. As part of this work, the Deliverable 6.1 report: **Analysis of current and emerging policies for data access/sharing, research use and transparency requirements**, was published in November 2023. This report scanned the European and international policy and legislative landscape regarding the processing and use of health data, including artificial intelligence (AI) and mobile applications for patients and focuses on important policy gaps. The report identified and signposted relevant instruments (e.g., laws, policies, standards, and guidelines) that IDERHA's work packages need to consider. A briefing template for summarizing instruments and an overarching topic map to guide the organization of these briefings has been developed. The report already contains several concise executive briefings on relevant instruments to provide actionable insights for IDERHA members. Further briefings will be filled in, updated, and extended during the project time to guide the IDERHA team in their work. This deliverable served as a resource for developing both the content in this report, but also guided the topics for discussion in stakeholder workshops held in 2024.
2. Through consideration of reports on recommendations regarding the European Health Data Space (EHDS), namely the deliverable reports from the first Joint Action Towards European Health Data Space (TEHDAS) project, as well as the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT) Think Tank's recommendations for the EHDS implementation. We have also considered the ethical principles developed by the Health Outcomes Observatory (H2O) project in this report.

Additionally, the Integrated Data Access Governance Council (IDAGC) that was established in the first phase of the IDERHA project, guided and advised the development of this report. The IDAGC includes senior leaders and experts who represent the perspectives of key stakeholders, including patients, academia, and industry.

We also note that in addition to the policy recommendations being developed in Task 6.3, a separate task in IDERHA, Task 6.4 is working on the **acceleration of policy development for the use of RWD and RWE** in regulatory and HTA decisions. IDERHA Deliverable 6.2, a scoping review of HTA and Regulatory RWD/RWE policy documents, was published in April 2024. The report identified priority areas requiring clarity for the next phase of policy work on RWD and RWE. Recommendations from Task 6.4 will be reported in separate deliverables.

Contributing projects and initiatives

The **European Health Data Space (EHDS)** is a major initiative by the European Union to create a unified digital infrastructure for health data across its Member States. The goal is to ensure that health data can be securely accessed, shared, and used for better healthcare delivery, research, innovation, and policy-making across Europe.

The **Joint Action Towards the European Health Data Space (TEHDAS)** is an European Union-funded initiative aimed at supporting the development and implementation of the EHDS, particularly in shaping policies and the technical infrastructure for the secondary use of health data across Europe.

The **European Institute of Innovation & Technology (EIT) Think Tank**, an initiative of the EIT, provides a platform for expert discussions and offers strategic recommendations on innovation policy. Its insights help inform EU policymakers and support projects like the EHDS.

The **Health Outcomes Observatory (H2O)** project, an IHI funded project, aims to unite the public and private sectors to establish a standardized data governance and infrastructure system across Europe with the focus on integrating patients' experiences and preferences into decisions that affect healthcare.

Current state of existing policy recommendations for data access and use for secondary purposes

In the course of our work, we identified several key resources that we considered as supportive to the development of our thematic areas and policy recommendations that aim to facilitate the access and use of heterogeneous health data for secondary purposes as described in the ['Methods'](#) section. While existing recommendations primarily address how to facilitate data access and usage considering the forthcoming implementation of the EHDS, we have selected these resources for their important insights, that are valuable not only for the EHDS implementation, but also for developing and sustaining data spaces of public-private partnerships like IDERHA. The recommendations derived from the above-mentioned projects primarily concentrate on the following key areas:

1. Aligning different national and EU-wide legal frameworks and establish common interpretations and standards

Health data-sharing for secondary purposes in the Member States of the European Union is hampered because of different national laws that have to be taken into account in addition to European-wide regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), but also upcoming regulations, such as the EHDS (TEHDAS Deliverable 5.4). Additionally, different interpretations of terms and definitions, national GDPR derogations, and varying preferences for choosing the legal basis for data processing under the GDPR create further obstacles (TEHDAS Deliverable 5.1). Across countries, there is no clear understanding of the roles in data processing, such as the differences between a controller, joint controller, processor, and data recipient. Furthermore, there are significant differences in how countries govern and manage health data systems, with each member state taking a different approach (TEHDAS Summary of Milestone 5.1 & 5.2).

Therefore, it is recommended to harmonize national regulations, legislations, and laws of the different Member States (including national GDPR derogations), and to better align these with European-wide regulations. A common interpretation of data anonymization and pseudonymization should be adopted to ensure legal clarity across Europe. This includes the definition of clear standards for sufficient anonymization and pseudonymization with flexible guidelines to adapt to technological advancements. It is recommended to provide an easy and public access to information about national rules governing secondary data use to enhance clarity for cross-border data-sharing. Additionally, the TEHDAS Deliverable 5.2 highlights that a suitable legal basis for data processing

for secondary use should be chosen, that aims to reduce reliance on consent-based data collection and prioritize public interest or legal obligations as the legal basis for health data use. Further recommendations in this deliverable report include that Member States should thoroughly examine and clarify the responsibilities of controllers and processors within their existing organization and infrastructure according to the GDPR, including how responsibilities are currently distributed and whether their roles should be further clarified in national legislation (TEHDAS Deliverable 5.2).

2. Improving data management and access procedures

Currently, according to the TEHDAS Summary of Milestone 5.1 & 5.2, there are no standardized data-sharing agreements in place for products developed by industry stakeholders using health data from the public sector. Standard policies for the secondary use of health data are essential and standards should be developed collaboratively with industry stakeholders and aligned with international standards. TEHDAS Summary of Milestone 5.1 & 5.2 states that establishing widely accepted guidelines and agreements on common rules for collaboration on quality registers between local authorities and the pharmaceutical industry is critical. Additionally, data use agreements should incorporate the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), with a strong emphasis on accessibility.

In the TEHDAS Summary of Milestone 5.1 & 5.2, an EU-level identification system, similar to the Participant Identification Code is proposed for streamlining data access requests. The use of aggregated data across regions is encouraged to minimize data sensitivity. The adoption of a clinical information model is recommended to improve the reuse of data from electronic health records (EHR). Furthermore, standardized metadata descriptions should be mandatory to ensure that essential information is consistently available. A national list of health data sources and data controllers, with a focus on research and well-described metadata, should be compiled. The definition of access protocols, the processing of data in secure environments, the consultation of National Research Ethics Committees, and the use of federated data integration for public data is recommended. The use of standardized terminologies and coding systems at the point of care, wherever feasible, alongside the development of a standardized data dictionary for data controllers to follow, is highly encouraged. Support for OpenData initiatives and portals, as well as further guidance on data management, with significant investments in IT infrastructure, are essential. Lastly, EHR systems should feature user-friendly interfaces that facilitate the registration of data (TEHDAS Summary of Milestone 5.1 & 5.2).

With the formal adoption of the EHDS legislation by the European Parliament in April 2024, many of these points have been addressed, as the EHDS aims to establish clear and consistent rules for accessing health data for primary and secondary use across Europe. The regulation particularly addresses the need for a common framework for the standardization of EHR systems across Member States, standard terminologies and coding systems, data access protocols, mandatory metadata catalogues, and the processing of data only in secure processing environments (Proposal for a Regulation on the European Health Data Space).

3. **Engaging with the public and promoting health and data literacy to enhance trust in data-sharing initiatives**

A public communication plan is recommended during the early stages of preparing national legislations on secondary data use (TEHDAS Deliverable 5.2). Furthermore, the TEHDAS Deliverable 8.2 encourages European policymakers to promote data altruism. Citizens should be actively involved, engaged, and empowered in health data altruism, tailored to the different needs and data literacy levels in the population and the sensitive nature of health data. Providing resources and training on data management and data privacy is essential. Citizens should have control over their health data, and organizations must be accountable and transparent about how and where data is shared, the benefits of sharing, and the created value for society. According to TEHDAS Deliverable 8.2, a variety of business models for voluntary health data-sharing should be encouraged, with careful consideration of the risks and benefits of the different models. With the formal adoption of the EHDS legislation, Member States can allow citizens to opt-out from the secondary use of their health data with some exceptions, e.g. research purposes in the interest of the public (Proposal for a Regulation on the European Health Data Space).

The EIT Think Tank report highlights that citizens' acceptance of using health data for secondary purposes varies by country and is influenced by concerns about data privacy and security, perceived societal benefits, and trust in authorities. Many people may be sceptical, but open dialogue and transparent communication can help alleviate these concerns. Building public trust involves direct engagement between data experts and citizens, showcasing concrete examples of data use. To ensure effective public engagement, the EIT Think Tank report highlights, that healthcare professionals must understand the importance of using data for secondary purposes, and patients should be empowered to advocate for its benefits. Promoting health and data literacy should be

integrated into the education for all EU citizens from an early age and educational strategies should match varying levels of data literacy. Extra support for vulnerable groups should be provided.

4. Establishing and maintaining high data security measures

When planning national legislations for the secondary use of health data, Member States should incorporate all areas of security from the beginning, including information security, cybersecurity, and IT security and consider security by design (TEHDAS Deliverable 5.2). There is a need to improve automated anonymization processes to prevent data breaches or de-anonymization (TEHDAS Deliverables 5.1 & 5.2).

5. Following an ethical framework for data-sharing and use

The TEHDAS Deliverable 5.4 recommends that the eHealth Network principles should apply to all legislative initiatives related to health data exchange at European and national levels, namely: base digital health on humanistic values, enable individuals to manage their digital health and data, make digital health inclusive, and implement eco-responsible digital health.

In order to become an approved researcher or organization within the H2O project, organizations must follow ethical principles for data use that the H2O project has developed. Firstly, health and health-related data may only be reused for purposes that directly aim to benefit society by improving health and care opportunities. Secondly, such data must never be reused for unethical purposes or those that violate human rights, disadvantage individuals or groups, or solely serve individual or organizational interests without societal benefits. Thirdly, the reuse of health data must prioritize the privacy of individuals by adhering to relevant data protection laws, implementing strong security measures, and using aggregated or anonymized data whenever feasible, while balancing this with the potential benefits of identifiable or pseudonymized data. Fourthly, any reuse of health data should respect the rights of data holders and comply with the agreed terms for data use. Fifthly, results from the reuse of health data should be published or shared unless they pose personal harm to identifiable individuals, could lead to discrimination against groups, or are intended for commercial purposes. Lastly, organizations that reuse health data are expected to maintain transparency with the public regarding their data usage and the outcomes of such uses.

6. Improving semantic interoperability

Semantic interoperability refers to the ability of different systems and organizations to exchange data and understand its meaning consistently. Key components include standardized vocabularies, consistent data models, contextual information, and clear definitions (IEC SMB/SG 12). Different interoperability standards throughout Europe impede the comparison and sharing of data and research findings. The TEHDAS Deliverable 5.1 report highlights important barriers to data-sharing with regards to semantic interoperability. The current SNOMED CT-Orphacode map lacks coverage for rare diseases, and differences in terminology hinder timely responses and lead to inefficiencies. Additionally, common models struggle with complex data. Semantic mapping to international taxonomies and ontologies impacts data usage from various data sources. Support for relevant taxonomies, ontologies as well as standards for Health Information Exchange is lacking in medical practice software, hospital information systems, and population health information systems. (TEHDAS Deliverable 5.1).

The TEHDAS Deliverable 6.2 report evaluated various standards for data discoverability, semantic interoperability, and interoperable communication between nodes. The authors recommend the use of a combination of generic and domain-specific standards to improve data discoverability involving two steps: first, gathering general knowledge about available datasets, and second, focusing on the specific content of the data source. Before adopting general standards, there should be discussions about the need for more detailed information, such as coverage and provenance, especially in health data. Domain-specific standards should also be adopted to enhance interoperability governance, aligning with the European Interoperability Reference Architecture (EIRA) and implementing conformity assessments. While no single standard can cover all relevant data types, institutions holding data can use existing standards like SNOMED CT as a semantic layer when standardizing their data. SNOMED CT is seen as the best-equipped ontology for covering medical concepts, but the current mapping is incomplete. There is also a need for semantic maps beyond medical concepts, covering social, cultural, economic, environmental, and genetic determinants of health. Data preparation for secondary use should go beyond concept mapping and include the development of comprehensive data models. For communication standards, DICOM and HL7-FHIR were identified as the most suitable by the TEHDAS Deliverable 6.2 report.

7. Allocating enough resources for the implementation and sustainability of data-sharing initiatives

7.i. Allocating enough financial resources

Financial resources are needed for the implementation of data-sharing initiatives. However, estimating these costs for the short and long term remains challenging. Regarding the implementation costs of the EHDS, the EIT Think Tank report revealed that smaller EU Member States will likely rely on EU co-funding to handle the financial burden, as the budget allocated by the European Commission is seen as insufficient for the project's ambitious goals. Efficient and equitable distribution of resources at EU and national levels is important for creating a system that benefits all stakeholders. A clear understanding is needed of which organizations will bear the costs, their investment capabilities, and the extent to which health institutions are expected to contribute. These institutions should not be overburdened with the costs of making data available for secondary use. Additionally, it is crucial to ensure that resources for EHDS implementation do not negatively impact patient safety and quality of care. The private sector, especially small and medium-sized enterprises, may struggle to meet the costs associated with their obligations as data holders, despite being key innovators in digital health. For data users, fair fees for data access will be essential. Cost-efficient implementation can draw on existing European projects that have developed technical solutions and data infrastructures. Pooling resources across organizations and Member States can foster standardized solutions and harmonized implementation, which is critical for the system's success. Beyond short-term funding, long-term financial mechanisms and new business models will be necessary to ensure the EHDS's sustainability over time.

7.ii. Allocating enough human resources and building capacity

The EIT Think Tank report highlights the need for specialized skills and human resources to establish and maintain the infrastructure for secondary use of health data within the EHDS framework. Data holders, like hospitals and research organizations, must allocate staff and resources to manage, standardize, and share their data. However, healthcare institutions already face obstacles due to limited capacity, staff shortages, and the technical complexity of managing data systems. Europe must address a wide skills gap in areas such as technical expertise, legal knowledge, and interdisciplinary skills to bridge medicine, IT, data science, and cybersecurity. Long-term investments in educational programs are essential for the success of data-sharing initiatives. Successful regional initiatives and contributions from industries like pharmaceuticals and digital health can serve as models and provide resources to support the EHDS's implementation.

The TEHDAS Deliverable 5.2 report recommends that Member States ensure comprehensive preparatory work when drafting proposals for laws on the secondary use of health data. This

preparation should include a detailed analysis of the resources required for implementation, not just in terms of financial investments for setting up new agencies or IT infrastructure, but also the human resources needed to operate these systems. It is essential to assess the additional resources required by data holders, as they will face new compliance obligations in the light of the EHDS.

8. Ensuring high data quality and improving primary use of data

The EIT Think Tank report stresses that the quality of data is crucial for deriving valuable results from its secondary use. Incomplete or biased data sets could lead to discriminatory outcomes. To avoid this, data must be interoperable across systems regarding technology, coding, and language. However, international data standards vary across Member States and healthcare settings, complicating uniform data quality. A common data quality framework is needed across all countries. Challenges include standardizing incomplete or outdated legacy data, particularly data from older citizens. Additionally, health institutions often lack financial and human resources to improve data quality. The EIT Think tank report stresses the importance of precisely defining data requirements and linking them to specific use cases. Regulatory data quality requirements vary across different types of applications and devices, especially for wellness apps, as they currently lack any standard evaluation guidelines. Researchers must be educated on the appropriate use of diverse datasets. Standardized methods for scientifically validating both the datasets and the algorithms need to be developed.

As the quality of secondary data relies on how well data is collected in healthcare settings, especially through EHRs, healthcare professionals (HCPs) play a key role in ensuring data collection meets both the needs for patient care and the research community's requirements. However, HCPs often lack the time or motivation to record information beyond what's needed for patient care. Technology could support HCPs, e.g. through automated data collection and integrated tools that support decision-making during data entry. To make sure innovative solutions derived from secondary use are widely adopted, the EU will need to develop standardized ways to evaluate and introduce new data-driven innovations into clinical care. Public-private partnerships will be crucial in ensuring these innovations address real healthcare needs.

The TEHDAS Deliverable 6.3 report emphasizes the creation of a comprehensive Data Quality Framework (DQF) that assesses both the technical quality and utility of health data to ensure it is suitable for its intended purpose. The DQF should prioritize key features such as relevance,

accuracy, reliability, coherence, and utility aspects like coverage, completeness, and timeliness. The framework also needs to account for the data holders' perspectives and should be applied throughout the data life cycle, from preparation and publication to preprocessing and enrichment. A maturity model is proposed to enhance data holders' management of data quality. All data holders should be assessed based on the maturity levels defined by the model, and consensus on the maturity should be included in the datasets metadata when shared. The framework calls for introducing semantic interoperability through international standards, with the European Commission fostering governance dialogue. Insights into data quality and utility must be formally defined through technical specifications, and the evaluation process should include self-assessments and external audits. Standardized metadata catalogues are required, and data management procedures should allow for pseudonymized dataset linkages. Privacy technologies should be applied without reducing data utility, enabling non-anonymized data use when necessary. Health data users should be incentivized to give feedback on data quality, and they must be informed of the importance of returning research outputs to enrich datasets, ensuring reproducibility and interoperability. Specific procedures for accepting and incorporating these enriched datasets should be developed.

Summary of existing recommendations

The existing recommendations provide an overview and valuable guidance on key factors to consider when facilitating data access and use for secondary purposes in Europe. While the recommendations are generally useful, they could require significant effort and resources to implement across each Member State, for example with regards to the improvement of data management and access procedures. It is essential not only to formulate recommendations but also to assess their feasibility and prioritize them, ensuring that decision-makers can effectively implement the most relevant and actionable recommendations.

Mostly, the existing recommendations incorporated feedback from experts in the field of IT, data science, and experts from the field of policy development. Feedback from other important stakeholders, such as patients and patient representatives, advocates for diversity and inclusion, and data protection officers (DPOs) and people working in similar roles were not always and not consistently included in the current recommendations.

The aim of this report is to give an overview of existing recommendations, identify gaps, and provide results from the initial set of workshops we have conducted in the first phase of the IDERHA project.

Additionally, we plan to gather feedback on the feasibility and prioritization of our recommendations through a public consultation in the first quarter of 2025. This will help streamline implementation and ensure the recommendations are well-aligned with the needs of key stakeholders.

Methods

Step 1: Developing initial thematic areas

To help understand key areas of concern in relation to data-sharing and access, and to begin developing high level recommendations to address these, we held four exploratory multi-stakeholder workshops in 2023 and 2024:

1. September 14, 2023: This workshop included nine participants from European patient organizations such as the European Cancer Patient Coalition (ECPC), Lung Cancer Europe (LuCE), and the European Patient Forum (EPF). The participants, including those affected by lung cancer (the focus of IDERHA's use cases), came from countries including France, Greece, Spain, Romania, and the UK. The workshop explored their understanding of health data, concerns over data fragmentation, and willingness to share data, emphasizing patient privacy, security, and the need for clear communication.
2. October 31, 2023: Ten experts from initiatives such as DARWIN EU®, EHDEN, and Gaia-X discussed challenges in data access, sharing, and integration. This workshop sought to identify the most impactful and feasible solutions for IDERHA to address, using lessons from similar projects to inform future policy recommendations.
3. June 20, 2024: Seven data protection officers (DPOs), information governance officers and people working in associated roles from across healthcare sector organisations in Europe that hold health data participated in this workshop. The aims of the workshop were to understand the challenges in assessing data access requests and solutions for these challenges as well as to explore possible nuances of such challenges and solutions depending on country and organisation type.
4. October 1, 2024: Ten representatives from different patient organizations and diversity and inclusion advocates participated in this workshop. We have gathered their opinions, concerns, and needs regarding the use of personal health data for research by discussing practical examples, such as how they feel about an opt-out option for the use of health data for secondary purposes and how news stories on data breaches and data misuse affect their willingness to share personal health information.

Each workshop aimed to understand the perspectives of a different stakeholder group on key aspects of data-sharing and access. The initial two workshops were more general in nature, seeking to identify key challenges and concerns with regard to data-sharing. The more recent two workshops, had a greater focus on exploring themes identified in the Task 6.2 gap analysis work – including how to build trust and transparency around data-sharing, consent mechanisms and addressing data breaches and misuse.

Each workshop was transcribed, and a summary report was produced outlining the key points made within the workshop. These key points allowed the team to understand the main areas of challenges or concerns regarding data-sharing and access for each particular stakeholder group. A copy of the workshop summary including key findings and suggested draft recommendations were sent to workshop participants to confirm if they felt this was reflective of what was said and to provide an opportunity for amends to be made. The full reports can be found in the Appendix, including the methods used to run each workshop.

Thematic areas and preliminary recommendations were developed:

- Using direct feedback from participants – when workshop participants provided actionable suggestions
- Using feedback indirectly from workshop participants – when comments were made about specific challenges or obstacles, the IDERHA Task 6.3 team considered what practical steps could be taken to address these using existing knowledge within the IDERHA consortium and recommendations from existing initiatives.
- Through insights gathered in IDERHA Task 6.2 (gap analysis) as to actions that need to take place to address gaps.

Step 2: Refining focus and developing detailed recommendations

The breadth of topics covered in this initial round of thematic areas and recommendations is wide, and we acknowledge it will not be possible to develop detailed technical recommendations in all these areas. The next stage of work within IDERHA Task 6.3, will therefore be to identify which of the thematic areas identified, should be taken forward for development.

Further details of our subsequent plans can be found in the '[Next steps](#)' section of this report and are summarised in the visual below.

Results

Ten thematic areas have been identified as potential topics to take forward to develop consensus recommendations. Where possible within each of the thematic areas, preliminary recommendations have been suggested.

- [Thematic Area 1: Aligning national and EU-wide legal frameworks and establish common interpretations and standards](#)
- [Thematic Area 2: Improve data management and access procedures](#)
- [Thematic Area 3: Engaging with the public and promoting health and data literacy to enhance trust in data-sharing initiatives](#)
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- [Thematic Area 10: Establishing a network for data-sharing initiatives to leverage alignment and synergies alignment and synergies](#)

Each thematic area discusses an aspect of data access, sharing or use that could be supported by additional and/or changes in policy. The recommendations under the thematic area are suggestions from the workshops undertaken within IDERHA, and not final. At this stage the thematic areas and recommendations have not been considered in terms of priority or feasibility, with the intention this will form part of the subsequent public consultation of this report. Questions that may require further development are suggested in the 'Potential areas for further exploration' section under each thematic area. These are not exhaustive lists but provide an indication of how the thematic area and the suggested recommendations could be expanded, if taken forward.

Thematic Area 1: Aligning national and EU-wide legal frameworks and establish common interpretations and standards

National regulations, laws, and legal frameworks of different Member States, including national derogations of European regulations, should be harmonized and aligned with EU-wide frameworks. This alignment should extend not only to legal aspects but also to the standardization of analytical processes and clinical definitions.

Specific recommendations:

Data protection & data use

- a. Providing enhanced guidance for Data Protection Officer (DPOs) on how to effectively comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), particularly regarding requirements for anonymization.
- b. Seeking to harmonize GDPR interpretations for health data use across Member States and providing sufficient financial and human resources for this.
- c. Explaining public value of data use, e.g. when evaluating data requests, DPOs must have a clear understanding of the purpose of data use to support their decision-making around risk and benefits.
- d. Clarifying the relationship between the European Health Data Space (EHDS) and GDPR, especially as new scenarios arise under the EHDS that will require other interpretations, introducing new challenges for DPOs.
- e. Seeking to standardize Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) formats to ensure consistency in how these are conducted.
- f. Developing guidance on performing risk assessments to determine if de-identified data is 'personal data' or not, including examples of 'good practice'.

Data-sharing

- g. Facilitating data access through creation of Secure Processing Environments (SPEs) or Trusted Research Environments (TREs), with data access protocols that promote uniformity, moving away from traditional data-sharing models.
- h. Providing clarity on practical requirements and risk mitigation measures for cross-border data transfers, particularly when data is hosted within the European Economic Area (EEA) but accessed from third countries and vice versa.
- i. Harmonizing potential national derogations regarding opt-out systems across different Member States and healthcare providers under the EHDS framework to avoid additional or new fragmentation in Europe and ensure citizens have the same rights wherever they are in the EU.

Source: These recommendations were derived from workshops conducted with DPOs, patients and patient representatives, diversity and inclusion advocates as well as with stakeholders working in data-sharing initiatives. They also include insights from IDERHA Task 5.3.

Who are these recommendations aimed at: These recommendations have been developed to input into the second joint action towards EHDS. To be actionable it would require support from national, member-state as well as European-level policy makers.

Time frame for implementation: 2-5 years

Implications for stakeholders: At a national level, governments face the challenge of adapting and implementing these policies within established data governance frameworks. As such, national data protection authorities must balance maintaining sovereignty over healthcare

governance whilst also contributing to European-level standardized frameworks. Some nations or governmental structures may be more resistant to adapting new policies, while others can be more permissive. At the European level, policy makers face the challenge of crafting flexible frameworks that accommodate national variation, building consensus between nations and ensuring the standardization and harmonization of fundamental data-sharing policies.

Other sources relevant to these recommendations:

- Different interpretations of terms and definitions, national GDPR derogations, and diverse choices for legal bases in data processing create obstacles in health data-sharing (TEHDAS Deliverable 5.1).
- There are significant differences in how countries govern and manage health data systems, with each member state taking a different approach. (TEHDAS Deliverable 5.1 & 5.2 Summary).
- Harmonizing national regulations, especially around anonymization and pseudonymization standards, and clarifying controller and processor roles under GDPR within Member States is recommended to facilitate legal clarity (TEHDAS Deliverable 5.2).
- Data-sharing across EU Member States faces challenges due to varying national laws on top of EU-wide regulations, with further complexity expected from the EHDS (TEHDAS Deliverable 5.4).

Quotes from workshops:

“Member States in in the European Union may have an additional national legislation which puts more restriction on top of the GDPR. That makes it difficult to have an exchange of health data across borders. In that case one should aim to harmonize national legislation.” (Researcher from a data-sharing initiative)

“Different institutions have different understandings of what [...] anonymized data is. We have the same contract framework agreements and there are different interpretations of the same article for at least 50% of the different institutions, depending on the countries.” (Data Protection Officer)

Potential areas for further exploration:

- Who should be responsible for providing support, training, and alignment opportunities for DPOs? At what level should this be targeted? (national, international, organizations, funders, DPOs).
- What specific aspects of GDPR need harmonizing? Should it be Member State existing laws that are harmonized or specific derogations?
- How do GDPR and EHDS policy makers see the landscape of policy evolving as the two begin to interact? What is a 'data intermediary' or a 'data altruism organization', what would it look like if we found one - are there any existing examples?
- How do other legislations e.g. Data Governance Act factor into this?

Thematic Area 2: Improving data management and access procedures

Data management and access procedures should be facilitated.

Specific recommendations:

- a. Determining which processes and procedures could be streamlined or improved to facilitate timely data access after request.
- b. Providing clear guidelines on the requirements and decision-making criteria for data access applications to ensure consistent approaches among Data Protection Officers (DPOs).
- c. Enhancing the training of DPOs on evaluating purposes of data access requests and emerging technologies to support their decision-making processes.
- d. Reviewing and refining how risk is assessed within Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIA).
- e. Setting realistic project goals that are aligned with the practical realities of the current data access landscape.
- f. Offering incentives for data-sharing and return, such as transparency on data usage, proper acknowledgment, and reciprocity, rather than or in addition to financial rewards (See also Thematic Area 9).
- g. Addressing industry concerns by ensuring the protection of trade secrets and commercial intellectual property.

Source: These recommendations were derived from workshops conducted with DPOs and stakeholders working in data-sharing initiatives. They also include insights from IDERHA Task 5.3.

Who are these recommendations aimed at: These recommendations have been developed to input into the second joint action towards European Health Data Space (EHDS).

Time frame for implementation: Up to 2 years

Implications for stakeholders: Data holders have to reassess and evaluate existing data governance frameworks and technical infrastructures and potentially develop new institutional competencies for data governance. Whilst larger institutions may be able to absorb these implications more readily, smaller organizations may struggle with adapting these new policies and risk widening accessibility gaps further. As such, data holders must ensure that this transformation and standardization of procedures enhances the healthcare data ecosystem, rather than burdening it and exacerbating inequitable data access.

Other sources relevant to this recommendation: The TEHDAS Deliverables 5.1 and 5.2 recommends establishing standardized policies in collaboration with industry, incorporating the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), and adopting EU-wide identification systems to streamline access. The EHDS legislation, adopted in April 2024, addresses many of these needs, promoting standardized EHR systems, secure processing environments, and consistent data access protocols across Europe.

Quote from workshop:

“One of the big barriers [...] was accessing the data. But I think, having the process [...] in place, and setting the expectations for what's needed by those who are both requesting the data as well as providing the data is very helpful [...]” (Researcher from a data-sharing initiative)

Potential areas for further exploration:

- Who should be responsible for providing support, training, and alignment opportunities for DPOs? At what level should this be targeted? (national, international, organizations, funders, DPOs).
- Understanding types of incentives that would support data-sharing across different stakeholder groups and explore if and how incentives could work in practice.
- Exploring difficulties that could arise with other than purely financial rewards, as questions as to who you would reward would arise (the patient for providing the data, the HCP for entering it in the system, the hospital for setting up the infrastructure etc.).

Thematic Area 3: Engaging with the public and promoting health and data literacy to enhance trust in data-sharing initiatives

Raising awareness about the benefits of sharing health data, dispelling misconceptions and allaying concerns can foster greater public support for data-sharing initiatives. The importance of clear and plain language communication to enhance data literacy among the general public, including minorities and people with low health and data literacy levels should be recognized, with the goal of encouraging a culture of data-sharing among both public and private institutions and the general public. This is an enabling factor for other thematic areas and recommendations. See also [Thematic Area 8](#) for linked recommendations – adequate incentives required to support these mentioned here).

Specific recommendations:

- a. Increasing funding for public education and wide-ranging communications campaigns on health data usage for secondary purposes and the promotion of data and health literacy.
- b. Educating citizens, data holders, and decision-makers about the benefits of sharing data for secondary use including successful case studies, and on risk mitigation strategies and safeguards in place to protect data security and privacy.
- c. Specific recommendations with regards to an opt-out option for secondary use of health data as envisioned by the European Health Data Space (EHDS) and on how to communicate to patients about their rights to control their data (See also [Thematic Area 1](#)):
 - i. Providing an opt-out system that is user-friendly and inclusive, with clear communication strategies targeted to all, especially minorities and those with low data and health literacy levels.
 - ii. Providing regularly updated information and lay language resources about potential purposes of secondary data use, stakeholders involved, and data types.
 - iii. Communicating what opting out means in practice, so that people can make informed choices.
 - iv. Actively engaging with citizens from diverse backgrounds, including those that have or continue to face discrimination, to thoughtfully address potential concerns with regards to the political and social contexts of secondary use of health data.
 - v. Acknowledging that emotional, behavioural, and not only rational factors play a role in opt-out decisions.
 - vi. Reassuring individuals who have opted out that their data is not being used for secondary purposes.
 - vii. Considering the reasons behind opt-out decisions for drawing accurate conclusions from datasets used for secondary purposes.

Source: These recommendations were derived from workshops conducted with patients and patient representatives, diversity and inclusion advocates as well as with stakeholders working in data-sharing initiatives.

Who these recommendations are aimed at: These recommendations have been developed to input into the second joint action towards EHDS. Patient and citizen education is likely to be most impactful coming from a variety of stakeholders, and the relevant stakeholders may vary by country. Nationwide education campaigns will be important; however, these should be co-created and implemented in close collaboration with patient and community organizations with whom there

may be greater levels of trust. Therefore, recommendations b and c should be considered by both governments and civil society organizations.

Time frame for implementation: Up to 2 years, 2 – 5 years, 5 years and beyond

Implications for stakeholders: Public bodies should provide funding for public engagement and educational activities and empower patient and other civil society organizations to promote health data literacy. Data holders, but also researchers should consider these recommendations in their daily work. Citizens should be included in the development and distribution of information material, making sure it is accessible and easily understood by everyone, especially people with low data and health literacy levels.

Other sources relevant to this recommendation:

- A communication plan for secondary data use legislation should begin early in the legislative process to increase transparency and public trust (TEHDAS Deliverable 5.2).
- TEHDAS Deliverable 8.2 states that policymakers should promote data altruism by actively engaging citizens, addressing data literacy levels, and ensuring resources for data management and privacy training.
- Public trust can be strengthened by involving data experts in direct dialogue with citizens and highlighting real-world examples of health data use (EIT Think Tank report).
- Education on health and data literacy should start early for all EU citizens, with additional support for vulnerable groups to ensure equitable understanding of data benefits and security (EIT Think Tank report).

Quotes from workshops:

“Unless people see the value of sharing data, you're not going to get any material. So I think there should be some work [on] how to improve people's health literacy and media literacy and just understand how data can save their lives, and that not all data collection is bad. [...] But there should be some real engagement with what is being done as opposed to just simply saying: Oh, yes, I agree, or just no, I don't agree.” (Patient representative)

“The idea should be to make it simple for the end users to understand what kind of studies there are and to understand which of the data is needed for it and make it easy for them to decide to participate if they wish to do so. Then this goes with [...] explainable and explained research [...] I mean, explain to the end user. We know from cancer, for example, that a lot of patient survivors' families would love to give away all their medical data for all kinds of research, but they don't even know where to give it to or what would be relevant for them.” (Researcher from a data-sharing initiative)

“And as long as both researchers and legislators pretend that this happens in a vacuum. I'm opting out. As long as it's an all-or-nothing approach, I'm opting out and I'm basically suggesting that everybody with a minority background opts out as well, because I think the political consequences of this are not thought through enough.” (Diversity and Inclusion Advocate)

Potential areas for further exploration:

What funding and resources are required to provide the right level of support to citizens on data-sharing, so an informed decision can be made?

What is considered an informed decision in this scenario?

Thematic Area 4: Establishing and maintaining high data security measures

Robust data security measures to protect citizens' rights and privacy should be prioritised.
Specific recommendations:

- a. Establishing legal frameworks to regulate access to, sharing of, and consent for health data within Member States where this does not exist currently; consider specific policies related to rare diseases.
- b. Ensuring that data cannot be and are not traced back to individuals.
- c. Providing comprehensive information to the public regarding measures to prevent data breaches and misuse. It should be ensured that this information is accessible and easily understood by everyone, particularly those with limited health and data literacy, as well as minority populations (see [Thematic Areas 3 & 5](#) for linked recommendations).
- d. Enforcing strict penalties for data breaches and misuses and conduct independent inquiries following such incidents to improve future security measures. Penalties may not solely include fines, but could, for example, also lead to restrictions to processing and using health data.
- e. Specific guidelines on communication to affected individuals should be developed, including apologies and explanations of any incidents, the actions taken, the consequences for data holders, available remedies for affected individuals, and actions affected individuals could take.
- f. Offering a wide range of authentication service providers to minimize risks, ensuring that the compromise of one provider does not impact a large number of individuals.
- g. Designating personnel specifically tasked with monitoring potential data breaches and misuses to ensure timely detection and response.

Source: These recommendations were derived from workshops conducted with patients and patient representatives, diversity and inclusion advocates as well as with stakeholders working in data-sharing initiatives.

Who are these recommendations aimed at: These recommendations have been developed to input into the second joint action towards the European Health Data Space (EHDS). They are aimed at member state governments and national policy makers.

Time frame for implementation: Up to 2 years, 2-5 years

Implications for stakeholders: Policymakers should provide the legal basis for these recommendations. All stakeholders and especially data holders and processors, such as researchers should apply these recommendations in their daily work and ensure enforcement.

Other sources relevant to this recommendation:

- Member States should integrate comprehensive data privacy and security measures, including information security, cybersecurity, and IT security, and consider security by design in national legislation for secondary health data use (TEHDAS Deliverables 5.1 & 5.2).
- Improving automated anonymization processes is needed to reduce the risk of data breaches and prevent potential de-anonymization (TEHDAS Deliverables 5.1 & 5.2).
- Expanded cybersecurity requirements now apply to healthcare organizations, mandating regular risk assessments, incident reporting, and improved cooperation between countries (Network and Information Security Directive 2).
- Strict compliance enforcement includes penalties and, in cases of serious negligence, restrictions on business operations to mitigate cybersecurity risks (Network and Information Security Directive 2).

Quotes from workshops:

“Especially for rare diseases [...] what are the policies [when it comes to data-sharing]? What are the constraints? What are the legal and ethical barriers? So I think that is an open issue in Europe that needs to be looked into.” (Researcher from a data-sharing initiative)

“There should be something like in the aircraft industry, where you can have an accident which can be fatal, and there are very serious investigations of what happened. There are consequences which actually improve the whole industry and it's a gradual building of technological skills in the infrastructure, but this also builds trust in the population.” (Patient representative)

“And while a fine might hurt them a little, it doesn't really hurt them depending on who they are. Probably not a lot. It doesn't have any consequences for them on how they use data in the future, [...] but if you had a data leak, whether intentional or just because you were lazy with the security, then one could say: You as an institution or as a researcher are not allowed to handle personal health data for five years.” (Inclusion and Diversity Advocate)

Potential areas for further exploration:

- How could non-financial penalties for data breaches and misuse work?
- What would be proportionate penalties for data breaches and misuses?
- Where would non-financial penalties not be suitable (e.g. restricting data storing and use would not be suitable for a hospital or healthcare provider)?
- How to ensure that penalties are not having the opposite effects of discouraging data collection and data-sharing, especially for cash strapped stakeholders like hospitals?

Thematic Area 5: Following an ethical framework for data-sharing and use

It is essential to ensure that research is patient-centered and demonstrably contributes to advancements in care options, public health, and individual and population benefits.

Specific recommendations:

- a. Actively involving patient organizations in all data-sharing processes for secondary use of health data, as this engagement fosters trust and ensures that the research questions and outcomes are relevant for the patients and meet their needs, e.g. inclusion of patients on internal governance structures, or guideline and framework development for data-sharing.
- b. Carefully managing secondary use of health data to ensure it never results in harm to individuals or groups. This includes taking measures to prevent any negative social, economic, or health-related consequences that could arise from how data is stored, used or shared. Safeguards should be in place to protect vulnerable populations and ensure that secondary use is always aligned with ethical standards, maintaining the privacy, dignity, and rights of all people involved. Researchers and legislators should acknowledge the political and social context in which data-sharing occurs and should be responsible for ensuring that people's privacy is protected.

Source: These recommendations were derived from workshops conducted with patients and patient representatives, diversity and inclusion advocates.

Who these recommendations are aimed at: All data holders who intend to share data e.g. Hospitals, registries, as well as those receiving data for secondary use e.g. Pharmaceutical/MedTech Companies and research/academic institutions, Regulatory and Health Technology Assessment bodies

Time frame for implementation: Up to 2 years

Implications for stakeholders: Data holders must develop new data governance frameworks as well as impact assessment tools to accommodate the implementation of an ethical framework. Stakeholders must demonstrate how their research directly benefits patients and how that concept underpins all of their research, study design and stakeholder engagement processes. Moreover, stakeholders must create transparent and practical frameworks and ensure that they are ethically compliant without hindering research activities.

Other sources relevant to this recommendation:

- eHealth Network principles, which are related to humanistic values, individual control, digital health inclusivity, and eco-responsibility, should apply to all health data legislation at European and national levels (TEHDAS Deliverable 5.4).
- Citizens should have control over their health data, with organizations being transparent and accountable about data-sharing, benefits of sharing, and societal value (EIT Think Tank report).
- Health data reuse should only serve societal benefits, prohibit unethical purposes, prioritize privacy, and comply with data protection laws, using aggregation or anonymization wherever possible (H2O project).
- Transparency with the public about data usage and outcomes is essential, and results should be published unless they risk harm, discrimination, or are for commercial purposes (H2O project).

Quotes from the workshops:

“Was a Patient Organization involved or is a Patient Organization involved in this type of research? Because I think this also would increase trust. If I know my Patient Organization is involved, and is a partner of this research project, then maybe [this organization] is one stakeholder that I can turn to if I have any concerns, any questions, et cetera.” (Patient representative)

“Sometimes you do need diversity information included in the research to ensure equality. But sometimes it could be a double-edged sword where actually we can work against equality because it could be used negatively to identify certain types of people and that information is actually detrimental to them or used in a detrimental way.” (Patient representative)

Potential areas for further exploration:

- How can we make sure that new ethical issues and risks tied to fast-growing Artificial Intelligence technologies are handled quickly and effectively?
- How to balance increased data accessibility in the context of for-profit research, and what would constitute appropriate compensation and specific conditions to grant access?
- How can we move to more “open-source” research and published results, especially as data is increasingly accessible, how to ensure equal and equitable access to data, research, and research results?

Thematic Area 6: Improving semantic interoperability

There is a huge diversity in health data sources available across Europe and globally. Secondary use requires increased data connectivity between these sources, which is supported proactively by alignment on shared data/technical standards. Enhancing interoperability across Europe should be a policy goal of all research and healthcare institutions, government agencies and funding bodies. Additionally, EU organizations who are significant users of secondary health data can also support this goal through requiring data to be available in alignment with key technical specifications for participation in wider EU projects.

Specific recommendations:

- a. Providing sufficient financial resources, skilled personnel, and building capacity for the improvement of semantic interoperability.
- b. Implementing structured formats for Electronic Health Records (EHRs) to ensure data is both searchable and accessible.
- c. Implementing fully interoperable health data systems across European countries and in line with international standards.
- d. Extending the use of EHRs for areas like primary care.
- e. Harmonizing data models and data dictionaries.
- f. Harmonizing key terminology where ambiguity remains e.g. pseudonymization.

Source: These recommendations were derived from workshops with stakeholders working in data-sharing initiatives and data protection officers and people working in similar roles. They also include insights from IDERHA Work Package 4.

Who these recommendations are aimed at: These recommendations have been developed to input into the second joint action towards European Health Data Space (EHDS). They are aimed at funding bodies of data sets e.g. healthcare institutions, research grants or policy makers such as regulators and HTA bodies who use data for secondary purposes

Time frame for implementation: 2-5 years, 5 years and beyond

Implications for stakeholders: Funding bodies must re-evaluate their funding priorities to support data collection, standardization and harmonization efforts, metadata collection and developing data models across different systems. As such, funding bodies must consider the increased costs of data collection and curation. Their funding decisions must consider the increased initial costs and the long-term benefits of more usable datasets. Lastly, funders must also develop performance metrics to evaluate how successfully semantic interoperability was implemented.

Other sources relevant to this recommendation:

- Different interoperability standards across Europe create barriers to effective data-sharing, as limited semantic interoperability and incomplete mappings, such as SNOMED CT-Orphacode for rare diseases, hinder efficiency and timely responses (TEHDAS Deliverable 5.1).
- Lack of support for relevant taxonomies, ontologies, and Health Information Exchange standards in medical and population health systems limits effective data usage across systems (TEHDAS Deliverable 5.1).
- Using a combination of generic and domain-specific standards can enhance data discoverability and interoperability, starting with general dataset information and refining to specific content, aligned with European Interoperability Reference Architecture (EIRA) (TEHDAS Deliverable 6.2).

- Standards like SNOMED CT are recommended as semantic layers, though there is a need for additional mapping to cover broader determinants of health (TEHDAS Deliverable 6.2).

Quotes from workshops:

“...EHRs [...] are going to be used more and more in federated networks. They are so different even within the same country. [...] So if you [have] a Spanish health record and try to compare it with the German one - it is totally impossible. (Data protection officer)

“I think one clear thing is to improve interoperability. So I think everybody will put this on the deck.” (Researcher)

Potential areas for further exploration (Hussein et al. 2024):

- Exploring evolving standards, such as the HealthDCAT-AP extension of DCAT-AP.
- Improving the Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) OMOP Common Data Model (CDM) so that it captures patient-generated health data effectively.
- Establishing thorough mappings between standards like FHIR and OMOP.

Thematic Area 7: Allocating enough resources for the implementation and sustainability of data-sharing initiatives

Both financial and human resources are needed to implement and sustain data-sharing initiatives. Additionally, it must be ensured that stakeholders involved in data-sharing initiatives have the relevant and sufficient skills and knowledge to implement and sustain these infrastructures, e.g. in the fields of medicine, IT, data science, and cybersecurity. This is an enabling factor for other thematic areas and recommendations.

Specific recommendations:

- a. Providing incentives and financial investments to maintain data-sharing infrastructures involving multiple actors in the short and long term. This will also increase motivation to continue the maintenance of data-sharing initiatives. (See also, [Thematic Area 8](#): standardizing incentives).
- b. Allocating enough financial and human resources for maintaining the accuracy of electronic health records (EHRs).
- c. Enhancing public funding for data documentation and data-sharing for both potential users and data holders.
- d. Providing training and support for data protection officers (DPOs), especially in the light of the upcoming European Health Data Space (EHDS) implementation, rather than just providing information to raise awareness of the impacts on their job. Support and training need to be easily understandable, with relevant examples and case studies for their work and not burdensome as many DPOs and people in associated roles are already overstretched.
- e. Promoting existing engagement opportunities for DPOs to connect, discuss problems, and understand solutions others have taken. Existing opportunities are not well known or not widely used due to limited resources from the DPOs side. Hence, organizations should also provide resources (dedicated time and funding) for DPOs to take part in these opportunities.

Source: These recommendations were derived from workshops conducted with stakeholders working in data-sharing initiatives and DPOs.

Who these recommendations are aimed at:

These recommendations have been developed to input into the second joint action towards EHDS. They are aimed at national governments and funders.

Time frame for implementation: 2-5 years, 5 years and beyond

Implications for stakeholders: National governments and funders must recognize that data-sharing needs sufficient resources, that will require sustained investment in infrastructure and human resources and requires consistent maintenance and alignment between regional and national funding priorities. Governments and funders must also recognize that beyond initial implementation costs, there is a need for sustainable funding to operationalize data-sharing initiatives (including data quality management, technical and security updates as well as workforce training). Stakeholders may also have to integrate new metrics for evaluation frameworks that assess the initial implementation and long-term sustainability of each initiative to ensure equitable access and maintain the integrity of data-sharing structures.

Other sources relevant to this recommendation:

- Smaller EU Member States may require EU co-funding for EHDS implementation, and a fair distribution of resources is needed to avoid burdening health institutions (EIT Think Tank report).
- Existing European projects that have developed technical solutions and data infrastructure, and pooled resources across Member States could promote cost-effective, standardized implementation (EIT Think Tank report).
- Specialized skills in technical, legal, and interdisciplinary areas are crucial for EHDS infrastructure, with significant investments in education required to address capacity and skills shortages within healthcare institutions (EIT Think Tank report).
- Member States should conduct thorough preparatory work for secondary health data legislation, including detailed resource assessments for financial and human investments in infrastructure and compliance needs for data holders (TEHDAS Deliverable 5.2).

Quotes from workshops:

“It is an infrastructure that consists of a lot of different actors that have to work together. And then not every actor sees the same benefit from the infrastructure as opposed to what they have to pay to maintain it, to have a connector in the clinic to have something that works on their systems where they don’t have an immediate benefit. But it costs some effort and money. That is definitely something that I see as a probable problem.” (Researcher from a data-sharing initiative)

“So yes, there are certainly awesome networks. And again, it does come down to resource. There end up being lots of different sorts of meeting we should be attending and we can’t. (Data Protection Officer)

Potential areas for further exploration:

- Who should be responsible for providing support, training, and alignment opportunities for DPOs? At what level should this be targeted? (national, international, organizations, funders, DPOs).
- Required resources and training for other stakeholder groups.
- Providing resources when necessary to support key stakeholders, including healthcare institutions and government agencies, to modernise their IT infrastructure and implement state-of-the-art security procedures.
- Ways to measure public health benefits that would justify and motivate Member States to invest in building the necessary infrastructure.

Thematic Area 8: Creating standardized incentives for data-sharing

Lack of incentives may hinder data-sharing and the establishment of data-sharing infrastructures - therefore incentivizing public and private entities as well as citizens to share data while ensuring transparent and ethical practices is essential.

Specific recommendations:

- a. Exploring incentives for citizens, especially when data is used for commercial aims.
- b. Explore incentives for data holders including consideration of those supporting data collection such as healthcare professionals.

Source: These recommendations were derived from workshops conducted with patients and patient representatives, diversity and inclusion advocates, and stakeholders working in data-sharing initiatives.

Who these recommendations are aimed at: These recommendations have been developed to input into the second joint action towards the European Health Data Space (EHDS). They are aimed at stakeholders who would want to utilize data for secondary purposes including pharmaceutical/MedTech companies and researchers.

Time frame for implementation: 2- 5 years

Implications for stakeholders: There are conflicting commercial interests and public benefit due to the varying priorities of each stakeholder. The varied interests of each stakeholder group bring about unique challenges and create complex dynamics around data access. For instance, larger industries or companies may exert greater influence in discussions about data access and distribution which may lead to inequitable data distribution and potentially inequitable access of their technology. Researchers on the other hand aim to use the data for advancing science and research, and might often seek larger, multi-source datasets to complete larger trials or analyses. However, they may also face resource constraints and are limited in the data they have access to. As such, it is important for all stakeholders to develop and agree on frameworks for incentivizing citizens that align with their priorities and interests.

Other sources relevant to this recommendation:

- Data altruism in the health sector should be promoted by fostering citizen participation, digital literacy, openness, and accountability, with support from a Rulebook for data altruistic organizations and collaborations with academia, public authorities, and non-profits (TEHDAS Deliverable 8.2).
- Revenue models for voluntary health data-sharing, involving private sector participation, should be explored to incentivize data-sharing while carefully balancing risks and benefits to complement the EHDS with additional public-use data (TEHDAS Deliverable 8.2).

Quotes from the workshops:

“We need [...] to think about incentives to satisfy the patients who share data, [but also] the hospital organizations. I mean the healthcare providers and physicians as well, [...] not just the patient is involved [...], it comes back to the main stakeholders (Researcher working in data-sharing initiative)”

Potential areas for further exploration: IDERHA should explore policy recommendations for creating standardized incentives, promoting data altruism, and establishing clear governance procedures including appropriate consent mechanisms.

Thematic Area 9: Exploring consent mechanisms

It is well established that access, use, and re-use of data is highly dependent on the willingness of the very subjects' who have provided the data in the first place. Consent to data use remains a complex issue, with current General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) stipulating the need for voluntary and reversible informed consent but also allowing the processing of sensitive data with legal bases other than consent such as public interest. There are significant differences in how these are applied amongst Member States. For-profit and non-profit organisations are also subject to different regulations. See also: [Thematic areas 1](#) (Alignment of legal frameworks)

Specific recommendations:

- a. Exploring the option for individuals to choose which research projects they consent to share their data with (instead of an all-or-nothing approach with regards to opt-out envisioned by the European Health Data Space (EHDS)), recognizing that people may have concerns about specific stakeholders or data types.
- b. Exploring how an opt-out system could work in practice (see also [Thematic area 3](#) for specific recommendations regarding an opt-out system).
- c. Ensuring transparency regarding the consent types utilized within a given situation as well as transparency on recipients, cross-border transfers, and purposes.

Source: These recommendations were derived from workshops conducted with patients and patient representatives, diversity and inclusion advocates, and stakeholders working in data-sharing initiatives.

Who these recommendations are aimed at:

Stakeholders who would want to utilize data for secondary purposes including pharmaceutical/MedTech companies and researchers. Private data spaces who have the flexibility to use different consent mechanisms.

Time frame for implementation: 2- 5 years

Implications for stakeholders: For data spaces of public-private initiatives: Under the EHDS framework, the opt-out system doesn't allow individuals to selectively choose the purposes or data users they wish to opt-out from, which may result in higher opt-out rates compared to a more granular system that offers such options. In contrast, private data spaces could provide users with the ability to define the specific conditions under which they are willing to share their data, giving individuals more control over their data.

Other sources relevant to this recommendation: Citizens would recommend being provided with the opportunity for meaningful and active decision-making in the secondary use of health data, as they value the ability to exercise control (TEHDAS Deliverable 8.1).

Quotes from the workshops:

"We know consent is a big issue, another one, that sort of been potentially raising desk researchers needing a lot of policy development." (Industry stakeholder)

Potential areas of exploration for further workshops:

- Can options other than blanket opt-out work for large-scale data-sharing initiatives such as EHDS?
- What consent mechanisms can private data spaces utilize to engender trust with citizens?

Thematic Area 10: Establishing a network for data-sharing initiatives to leverage alignment and synergies

Stakeholders mentioned a lack of reuse of learnings and cooperation across European Union (EU) funded research projects and the need for a research memory to avoid duplication of work.

There were no specific recommendations given on how to achieve this by workshop participants, however insights from IDERHA partners suggest:

- Explore establishing standardizing processes and frameworks e.g. data access agreements, legal frameworks, that sit outside of individual projects from same funder, to prevent duplication of effort and save time and money.
- Better coordination of funding across the EU to avoid funding of similar projects.
- Incentives for publishing project results in scientific literature.

Source: These recommendations were derived from a workshop with stakeholders working in data-sharing initiatives.

Who are these recommendations aimed at: Although there are no specific recommendations within this thematic area, recommendations could be further developed with EU research funders and members of current and previous EU funded research projects that have had a focus on the access and sharing of health data.

Time frame for implementation: 2 to 5 years

Implications for stakeholders: Several data-sharing initiatives exist, and collaboration between these projects is crucial. Public consultations on key projects provide a valuable opportunity to review and offer feedback on others' work, make recommendations, and share insights to prevent duplication and ensure consistency in areas such as legal, ethical, and technical considerations. There is currently no overarching network or organization dedicated to fostering collaboration among EU-funded data-sharing initiatives related to secondary use of health data. IDERHA has begun identifying relevant projects for collaboration and is planning how to best leverage alignment and synergies.

Other sources relevant to this recommendation: No published recommendations or initiatives that we are aware of.

Quotes from workshops:

"[We need] a big data network, but also a big community around that. And finally, an important thing is a research memory. So how do we make sure that we are not redoing the same job over and over again? There are many people in Europe that have tried to define patients with diabetes in databases. Why are we doing that? It's a stupid thing." (Researcher working in data-sharing initiative)

Potential areas for further exploration:

- What kind of function would be best suited to collate learnings across projects/create a 'research memory' – a separate project, a repository?
- How would this be monitored and maintained?
- Who would be best placed to have responsibility for this?
- Encourage dissemination and high quality of research outcomes after the end of the project and integration of project learnings into policies and regulatory practices to bridge the gap between researchers and policy makers.

Discussion

This deliverable represents the initial findings and thematic areas for establishing multi-stakeholder consensus policy recommendations for data-sharing, access and use governance policies. Through a series of exploratory workshops with key stakeholders—including DPOs, patients and patient representatives, diversity and inclusion advocates, and participants involved in data-sharing initiatives—ten thematic areas were identified. These thematic areas capture the diverse challenges and opportunities in aligning national and EU-wide legal frameworks, enhancing data management, building public trust, ensuring high data security, and promoting semantic interoperability, among others. The thematic areas offered in this report are high-level but are aligned with results found in other initiatives to address these challenges, such as TEHDAS reports. They highlight the complex nature of these issues and the need for continued multi-stakeholder engagement to develop solutions that are nuanced, feasible and targeted at specific stakeholders.

Strengths and Limitations

The thematic areas and recommendations in this report remain broad having been developed through a relatively small number of exploratory workshops conducted thus far, which restricts the depth of detail and the granularity of the initial findings. Moreover, synthesizing feedback from diverse groups and balancing differing interests can be challenging and may require further refinement. To develop targeted, actionable recommendations, additional workshops and consultations are needed to ensure the next phase of work focuses on practical feasibility and implementation.

A major strength of this report lies in its inclusive approach. The thematic areas and preliminary recommendations were shaped by direct input from a diverse range of stakeholders, ensuring the report reflects the varied needs and perspectives of those engaged in health data access and sharing. By integrating insights from key stakeholders such as patients, and DPOs, the thematic areas and recommendations capture a well-rounded view of the current landscape. Notably, efforts were made to involve stakeholders, such as DPOs, who may not have been consulted in similar initiatives before, adding depth and breadth to the findings.

The report recognizes that while the identified thematic areas address significant aspects of health data governance, they do not cover every relevant issue. Topics such as data quality were highlighted by stakeholders as crucial but were not fully explored within this deliverable due to the focus on data access and sharing. Data quality is being addressed in a related task within the IDERHA project (Task 6.4), in relation to RWE. Additionally, issues like the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and the use of synthetic data for health research are acknowledged as emerging themes that warrant further exploration.

Next steps

Moving forward, IDERHA task 6.3 aims to build on this foundational work by conducting a public consultation in early 2025. This consultation will:

- Determine which thematic areas should be taken forward to further expand and refine the recommendations within it.
- Determine if there are any other key thematic areas that are felt to be of high priority that should be considered.
- Seek input on the feasibility and priority of individual recommendations, including areas for further exploration, target audiences and implementation considerations.
- Understand how we can go beyond what has already been recommended by other initiatives.

Ongoing engagement with stakeholders throughout this iterative process will be essential to ensure that recommendations remain relevant and practical. Transparent communication will play a key role in aligning these policies with real-world needs and enhancing their applicability.

The aims and priorities of this work will also be influenced by the findings of the final report from IDERHA Task 6.2 whose role, in part, is to scan and identify policy and legislative gaps in the European and international landscape that have a bearing on the acquisition, collection, processing and use health data, particularly regarding the IDERHA project. The report, *“D6.4 Updated analysis of current and emerging policies for data access/sharing, research use and transparency requirements”*, is due to be released in May 2025. We will continue to work closely with the partners delivering this report (DEFACTUM, IHD) to consider how to address the policy gaps raised.

Following this, we will bring together technical experts to further develop and detail these recommendations, ensuring that they are practical and can be effectively implemented. The project will continue to consider results from related European initiatives such as TEHDAS2, QUANTUM, and the EHDS2 pilot to leverage shared insights and promote alignment across health data policies. This iterative process will ensure that policy recommendations not only address current challenges but also remain adaptable to future developments in health data governance. This is the first iteration of three deliverables, with the aim to develop more targeted and actionable recommendations by March 2027.

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IDERHA Task 6.3 Patient workshop 14/09/2023 - Full report

Introduction

The IDERHA project launched its multi-stakeholder workshop series on 14 September 2023, aimed at supporting its work on developing consensus on policy recommendations concerning the access, sharing, and integration of health data.

The inaugural workshop brought together nine members of the public who belong to three of IDERHA's patient organisation partners, the European Cancer Patient Coalition, Lung Cancer Europe, and the European Patients' Forum. Representatives from France, Greece, the Netherlands, Romania, Slovakia, Spain, Turkey, and the UK attended the workshop. The patient representatives had diverse backgrounds, and many had personal experience with cancer or had close family members who had been affected by the disease.

The decision for the first workshop to be patient focused, reflects the importance of patient input within IDERHA. Patient voice will play a major role in the development of consensus on policy recommendations regarding ethical and legal governance of heterogeneous health data access and sharing. The patient participants all rated themselves as having an average or significant understanding of how health data is currently used. In addition, 13 IDERHA members were in attendance.

During the workshop, participants received an introduction to the IDERHA project, gaining insights into how the project aims to change how health data can be used in the future for patient and research benefit. Workshop participants were encouraged to discuss their opinions on IDERHA's objectives and express any potential concerns they may have.

What is health data?

To begin discussion, participants were asked to share their perspectives on what health data meant to them. Participant comments included:

- Health data encompasses patient information covering various aspects, such as vital metrics like blood pressure and a patient's treatment history, both current and past. It was emphasised that for individuals dealing with rare diseases or specific conditions, sharing health data was critical for understanding what treatments worked and what didn't, leading to potential adjustments in their treatment plans.
- Health data refers to any information related to an individual's health, creating a unique and personal connection to that person.
- The broad spectrum of health data was discussed, including data collected from individuals for example collected by healthcare professionals. The importance of considering information

about the health of a group or population of people was highlighted e.g., types of mutations, and data sources such as biobanks.

- Confidentiality in health data was also discussed. It was suggested that patients may be hesitant to share their personal data with others. This raised the sensitive issue of how far one's personal health data should be shared with external parties, particularly for research or healthcare purposes for example, people might be more reluctant when commercial organisations use their data.

Understanding of how health data is used

Participants were asked in a poll to rate their own perceived level of understanding of how their health data is currently used, with the following options: no understanding, little, average, good or significant understanding. All participants rated themselves as having an average or significant understanding of how health data is currently used, reflecting a relatively informed group of individuals.

It was highlighted that this group of empowered patients might have a greater level of understanding than the general population. It was also noted that while they have a good understanding of what health data is, they have limited knowledge about how it is being used. This nuanced view pointed out the importance of distinguishing between understanding what data is and comprehending its actual usage.

Concerns about data fragmentation and data-sharing

Participants were asked how concerned they were about the current fragmentation of health data, they were asked to score from 1 to 10, where 1 was not at all concerned and 10 was extremely concerned. The responses varied, reflecting diverse viewpoints within the group (Figure 1).

Concerns about the fragmentation of health data

Figure 1. Participant concerns about the fragmentation of health data (1 – Not at all concerned, 10 - Extremely concerned)

Participant comments regarding their level of concern about the fragmentation of health data included:

- A participant who scored “10”, indicating extreme concern, pointed out the importance of breaking down data silos, especially concerning compassionate use programs, as fragmented data could lead to critical information not being shared between healthcare providers (doctors and pharmacists).
- A “9” score highlighted the difficulties they faced as a patient who used two different international healthcare systems. These systems were not interoperable, requiring manual translation of documents and data-sharing between different healthcare providers. They also flagged the importance of sharing data for rare diseases where few people have the condition.
- An “8” score reported their experiences when they were a patient and how they had to manage data from different healthcare entities, such as labs, pharmacies, and hospitals, which were not connected. This experience was challenging, and they emphasised the need for better data exchange and integration, particularly to relieve patients of the burden of managing their own data. They were able to manage it but could imagine that this is not possible for everyone and that this would cause many losses.
- A “7” explained that on the one hand, data privacy is important, but on the other hand, if there is no integration of the data, it is almost impossible to diagnose people in early stages of the disease especially for diseases that require early detection to save lives. They brought up the term “silent killer”.

- One individual who scored a “4” expressed an understanding of the fragmentation issue but noted that their personal level of concern was low. They suggested that the benefits of data integration might outweigh concerns.
- Another participant described themselves as not being concerned that the data is fragmented, but more concerned about the reuse of the data. They noted that there is a need for a legislative framework before trying to find methods to put these data together. It would be important to ensure that the patient’s rights and privacy are protected.

Reservations about sharing health data

Participants were asked how much they agree or disagree with the following poll question “I have reservations about sharing my health data”. Scoring on a scale of 1-10, where 1 is completely disagree and 10 is completely agree. All participants scored a 5 or lower, suggesting that this particular group were not as concerned about sharing their health data (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Do participants agree or disagree with the statement ‘I have reservations about sharing my health data’ (1 – Completely disagree, 10 - Completely agree)

Participant comments included:

- There is a need for clarification regarding sharing health data with medical professionals, compared to sharing with others outside the healthcare system. They indicated a willingness to share data with healthcare providers but emphasised the importance of a legislative framework when sharing data with non-medical entities. They also emphasised the importance of protecting patients’ rights when sharing health data.
- One’s willingness to share health data may depend on various factors, including cultural and age-related aspects. They explained that older people may be more willing to share their

data, as opposed to younger people. They also explained that if the data was aggregated, there may be more willingness to share their data, than if it was identifiable.

- The security of data is an issue, thus highlighting the need to ensure data security and prevent unauthorised access, especially in the context of hackers potentially targeting health data.

IDERHA project details

In this section of the workshop, Lena Hegel discussed the practical aspects of the IDERHA project, and its benefits. The themes discussed included, data sources, federated data infrastructure, data security, data integration, AI algorithms, clinical decision support, and individual benefit. Workshop participants were given the opportunity to comment on this. Comments included:

- Concerns about the lack of data standardisation in health records. In response, it was described that there is a work package dedicated to data standardisation and the use of the OMOP common data model to achieve this.
- Possibility of diagnosis depends on the country and resources of the health care system. Hence, the data quality and completeness of the data would depend very much on the country and the conclusions drawn from these data could be biased.
- There was a question about how the project plans to provide patients with access to their data, especially regarding sensitive information like cancer prognosis. It was clarified that the application primarily helps patients organise and give consent for their data but doesn't directly communicate sensitive prognostic information.
- There were concerns about patient attitudes toward testing and data uptake, as well as the challenges of clinicians identifying relationships between symptoms and conditions.

Opinions and key concerns from patients' perspectives on the IDERHA project

In this part of the workshop, the discussion centred around the participants sharing their thoughts and concerns regarding the project. The following themes were identified:

- Positive Feedback: Participants expressed overall support for the IDERHA project, recognising its importance and necessity in the field of precision medicine. They highlighted the need to break down data silos, integrate different types of health data, and make data more accessible for research and decision-making.
- Concerns on Communication: Concerns were raised regarding effective communication, especially with patients and the general public. Participants stressed the need for clear and plain language communication to ensure that all stakeholders, including patients, can understand the project's goals and processes. Proper communication about data collection and consent was emphasised.
- Importance of Data Literacy: It was noted that improving health literacy and media literacy is vital. The general public needs to understand how sharing data can benefit them and that not

all data collection is harmful. Raising awareness and understanding the value of data-sharing is crucial.

- **Security and Trust:** Security and trust were highlighted as significant challenges. Participants emphasised the need for strong data security measures and trust-building mechanisms to ensure public and patient willingness to share data. Participants also discussed the challenges in getting the public to agree to data-sharing and how to maintain the relationship of trust with individuals and communities.
- **Data Privacy:** Privacy and ensuring individuals have control over their data were key concerns. The project needs to guarantee data privacy and provide transparency in data handling and consent processes.
- **Data Accessibility and Usefulness:** Another concern was ensuring that the data collected is made accessible, and that it is useful for improving healthcare and research. Generally, perceptions were positive.

Feedback on the benefits and concerns of the project

In this section, the benefits of the project were explained. The benefits were categorised into three main areas: research, healthcare organisations, and individuals. The integration of data would allow faster and cheaper research using high quality data. This would allow to improve patient's outcomes. The patients will be able to decide which data they share for which purposes. This discussion underscored the significance of privacy, consent, and legal support in ensuring the success and acceptance of the IDERHA project. The discussion included the following patient input:

- The necessity of an EU resolution for the establishment of a European legislative framework to support patients' consent and data security was highlighted, stressing that patients wouldn't provide consent without these protections.
- People generally don't have issues with sharing data but there was an emphasis on the responsibility of handling data correctly. They also referred to upcoming European legislation and the need to raise awareness about data privacy and protection.

Topics for future workshops

The workshop concluded with a final poll discussing which topics could be the focus for further patient workshops. Participants were given the following 5 options: data quality and linkage; new AI tools; consent; secondary use of data for evidence in developing and assessing medicines; anonymisation/pseudonymisation. All topics received at least one vote, indicating an appetite for

more workshops. Other suggested topics included what data patient participants would like to see collected across Europe, and data collection.

Conclusion

The IDERHA patient workshop revealed valuable insights into participants' perspectives on the project and health data in general. It highlighted the diverse nature of health data, emphasising its significance for individuals dealing with rare diseases and the need for comprehensive, yet understandable communication about data collection and consent. The participants' concerns revolved around data fragmentation, security, and the legislative framework to protect patient rights and privacy. They recognised the potential benefits of the IDERHA project but stressed the importance of privacy, trust, and data literacy in ensuring its success. This workshop provided a platform for patients to voice their views and identified key areas, such as data quality, AI tools, and consent, for future discussions and collaboration.

Appendix

Attendees

The patient workshop consisted of 9 participants representing various IDERHA patient organisations, including the European Cancer Patient Coalition (ECPC), European Patients' Forum (EPF), and Lung Cancer Europe (LuCE). The participants had diverse experiences, with individuals either having personal experience with cancer, or having family members affected by cancer. The participants were from a wide range of European countries, including Spain, the UK, France, Romania, Slovakia, Turkey, Greece, and the Netherlands, providing a wide range of perspectives and insights.

There were 13 IDERHA members in attendance including:

Name	Organisation
Alfonso Aguarón	Lung Cancer Europe
Ravinder Claire*	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence
Heather Colvin	Johnson & Johnson
Katharine Cresswell*	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence

Dominik Geller	Hygiaso
Lena Hegel*	Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft
George Kolostoumpis	European Cancer Patient Coalition
Rebecca Lumsden*	Sanofi
Kathrin Morasek	Ludwig Boltzmann Institut/Medizinische Universitaet Wien
Simon Scheider*	Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft
Tanja Stamm	Medizinische Universitaet Wien
Gözde Susuzlu	European Patients' Forum
Morten Deleuran Terkildsen	DEFACTUM

*Speaker

Workshop agenda

Agenda item	Speaker/Moderator
Introductions and welcome	Ravinder Claire
Overview of IDERHA	Ravinder Claire
Problems around data-sharing and linkage	Rebecca Lumsden
How IDERHA is tackling these problems	Lena Hegel/Simon Scheider
Benefits of IIDERHA	Katharine Cresswell
Discussion	Katharine Cresswell

IDERHA Task 6.3 Data stakeholder workshop 31/10/2023 - Full report

Introduction

Following the launch of a series of multi-stakeholder workshops, with the first workshop focusing on the patient's perspective, the IDERHA project held its third multi-stakeholder workshop on 31st October 2023. The online workshop gathered 10 key stakeholders from the health data ecosystem, see appendix 4, focussing on the areas of data access, sharing, and integration. The primary objective was to highlight the necessities for developing new policies and frameworks to support better health data integration across Europe. The workshop aimed to hear the perspectives of stakeholders already engaged in the data-sharing and integration space, seeking to understand what IDERHA is best placed to deliver in terms of building policy recommendations for supporting data-sharing and integration. Specifically, the aims were:

- To explore differences, synergies, and interconnections of IDERHA with other data projects
- To understand gaps or challenges in policy requiring consensus building
- To identify areas with existing best practices or relevant consensus on guidance around data-sharing and integration
- To explore what needs to be done to ensure the successful sustainability of policy recommendations

Methodology

During the workshop, participants received an introduction to the IDERHA project, gaining insights into how the project aims to change how health data can be used, accessed, and shared. Workshop participants were encouraged to discuss their experiences and lessons learned from similar projects that could be helpful for IDERHA.

To facilitate the discussion and for visualisation, Miro board was used (<https://miro.com>). In the first of three tasks, workshop participants were asked to identify their top barriers and challenges to data access and sharing. Subsequently, participants were asked to place their virtual sticky notes on a scale allowing for the visualisation of which identified barriers and challenges were more or less likely to be affected by policy change (Appendix 1).

Participants were then asked to move their sticky notes on to a quadrant chart, providing a visualisation of which of their barriers and challenges were both feasible and impactful (Appendix 2).

Top barriers and challenges to access and sharing of data

To begin the discussion, participants were asked to share their top barriers and challenges to access and sharing of data that they have identified from working in this area. The identified barriers and challenges included:

- Harmonisation and interoperability
 - Lack of shared terminology e.g., for pseudonymisation, clinical definitions and analytical definitions
 - Limited interoperability/lack of resources to achieve interoperability

- Lack of interoperability standards
- Cloud solutions owned by third parties (outside of EU¹)
- Culture
 - Lack of data-sharing culture i.e., people want access but are not willing to share - particularly at the organisational level
 - Distrust around data-sharing across stakeholders especially for citizens
 - Lack of or non-standardised incentives to share data and/or setting up infrastructure
 - Lack of reuse/cooperation across European Union (EU) funded research projects
- Legislation & governance
 - Lack of harmonisation of legislation and governance procedures at an EU, national and organisational level
 - Differences in interpretation of legislation including General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and national policy
 - Challenge to international data flow
 - Management of granular on-going consent for primary and secondary usage of data
- Data access
 - Short timelines for procedures and processes to access data
 - Lack of clarity on requirements and decision-making in data access applications
 - Lack of realism when defining project goals - not aligned to the data access situation “on the ground”
 - Access to decision-makers who have the power to share data
- Data quality
 - Limited quality/completeness of data sets
 - Bias within data sets

Interoperability, culture change/trust building, and legislative and governance uncertainty issues were the most frequently mentioned topics.

Peter Rijnbeek, executive director of the DARWIN EU® Coordination Center, and coordinator of European Health Data and Evidence Network (EHDEN), emphasised the importance of improving interoperability, standardisation of analytical pipelines and phenotypes of certain diseases, and aligned definitions of study types. While most analytics are done using aggregated data, rare diseases may require specific policies, constraints, legal, and ethical considerations. He also emphasised the importance of a “research memory” to avoid repetition.

Christian Buggedei from Charité working on the project Gaia-X, highlighted problems in maintaining the infrastructure, but felt this could be easily solved through policy. However, a complex infrastructure involving multiple actors, costs effort and money and may need incentives to be maintained in the longer term.

Harald Wagener, also from Charité working on the project Gaia-X, stated that while there is consensus on the importance of sharing data by clinicians and researchers, there is also hesitancy in sharing these data and felt that this cannot be easily solved with regulations.

Shahid Hanif, Managing Director of the GetReal Institute, highlighted that the IMI GetReal project experienced a number of challenges accessing data for a variety of reasons, including the complexity of the process to access research-ready data in a timely manner as one significant barrier. Establishing a clear and reliable process regarding the request and timely provision of research-ready data is of importance.

Niklas Hedberg, who is involved in the project EUnetHTA-21, highlighted that decision makers mostly put emphasis on the risks rather than on the benefits of data-sharing, since there are very few successful examples and pilots of use cases, that would ease trust building. Shahid Hanif added that decision makers must be clearly informed about strategies for risk minimisation. Christian Buggedei stated that data-sharing through citizen consent is encouraged, ensuring that people consent before data is transferred or processed. However, the challenge of this approach is that the data owners need to be contacted and it might be difficult to find them. He states that the German Health Minister introduced the term “Study Tinder”, which could be used to allow people to choose whether and in what study they would like to participate by contributing their data. Harald Wegener added to this, that the goal should be to make it easy for end users to understand the types of studies, the data needed, and the reasons for participating in such studies.

Dipak Kalra, President of the i-HD, added that educating the public about the value of using health data for the benefits of patients remains an activity undertaken by bodies with limited budgets.

Rada Hussein, Principal Investigator at Ludwig Boltzman Institute, stated that data and data ownership is currently discussed in Europe with a similar focus as in the United States. Depending on who owns the data, incentives to share data should not only be given to patients, but also to hospitals and healthcare providers. She referred to the health data governance principles (<https://www.healthdataprinciples.org/>) that were used in creating the governance model of HL7-Patient Contributed Data.

Sebastian Gerbholz, from Atos working on the Gaia-X project, mentioned the need for small pilot projects, that enable to get to the big picture in the end, such as the Gaia-X reusable blocks that will be used in the ambitious European Health Data Space (EHDS) pilot project.

Barriers and challenges that could be most influenced by policy change

Participants were asked about which of the identified barriers and challenges they felt could be most influenced by policy change. They were asked to place these on a scale from ‘Can’t be influenced by policy change’ to ‘Can be influenced by policy change’ on an online Miro board. A summary of the key results can be seen in figure 1; the full results can be found in appendix 3.

Figure 1 - Summary of key results of likelihood of barriers to be influenced by policy change. Light grey circles indicate key differences in participants' opinions on placement.

Issues surrounding legislative and governance rules and procedures, generally tended to be classed as having a higher likelihood of being influenced by policy change. Whereas, creating culture change to one of greater openness to data-sharing, was generally felt to be less policy sensitive. It should be noted that this was a subjective exercise, meaning there were some discrepancies in participants' perceptions of how much certain topics could be influenced by policy change, such as hesitancy of data holder to share their data.

Other issues that were perceived to be likely to be impacted by policy change include the limited quality and completeness of data sets, lack of data availability, and public funding. The lack of interoperability and data standards, and the complex application process of data access were perceived as problems that legislation was unlikely to solve.

Michel Silvestri, Head of Unit of the Swedish eHealth Agency, pointed out that the legal uncertainties are likely to be solved by policy. As some EU Member States may have additional legislations on top of the GDPR that could restrict cross-border health data exchange, the EHDS legislation could remove those barriers once it is implemented.

To enhance lack of trust of citizens and data holders, Shahid Hanif mentioned that transparency is needed from the bodies aiming to access and process the data.

Barriers and challenges that would be most impactful and feasible for IDERHA to address

Participants were asked to assign the identified barriers and challenges according to the impact they might have for the IDERHA project and according to the feasibility that they can be addressed within the IDERHA project. The key results are summarised in Figure 2.

Most of the challenges were classed as impactful with the majority being also perceived as feasible. Again, as a subjective task there was some disagreement, for example lack of trust, data altruism, data quality and interoperability, were all placed as different levels of feasibility and impact by different participants. This is perhaps reflective of the different experiences of the participants, and

their general outlook on what is achievable. It is perhaps unsurprising, however, that most of the challenges were seen as impactful, as they had already been identified by the workshop participants as being their top perceived key challenges.

Figure 2 - Summary of key results of activity rating feasibility and impact of addressing barriers. Light grey circles indicate key differences in participants' opinions on placement.

Some of the barriers/challenges classed as most impactful and feasible to address included:

- Incentivisation for data-sharing
- Consent by citizens/patients for primary and secondary data use
- Governance models
- Increasing public funding on data-sharing and access

Some of the barriers/challenges classes as impactful but with lower feasibility included:

- Different organisational cultures and barriers
- Cloud solutions owned by third parties
- Standardising clinical definitions across databases
- Getting decision makers to sign off data-sharing

Shahid Hanif stated that the challenge lies in identifying the key policy focus areas that can be impacted within the time frame of IDERHA. The focus could be on a whole range of policies with regards to different stakeholders or specifically on e.g. the EHDS. For enhancing the effectiveness of the work in IDERHA, Sebastian Gerbholz mentions the importance of reusable building blocks and cooperation across different projects.

Advice for the IDERHA project

To close the discussion, the participants were asked about advice they would give to themselves if they were undertaking a project like IDERHA, for example regarding actions or considerations at the earliest stages of the project to ensure best chances of policy recommendations being actionable.

Shahid Hanif suggested that it may not be enough to simply publish policy recommendations without laying out a path for others to follow. The policy recommendations should be addressed to specific target groups to be feasible. It is important to define and prioritise specific tasks focusing on impactful changes. He highlighted the importance of understanding previous political recommendations, important key drivers of change, identification of stakeholders, and failure-prone experiences to avoid repeating previous mistakes. Regarding this, Niklas Hedberg stated the importance of learning and analysing the reasons behind decisions that agencies did or did not make.

Shahid Hanif also mentioned the importance of communicating with the broader community and to actively ask for feedback.

Phillip Gribbon, IDERHA project leader, pointed out that the policy recommendations should be annotated with concrete examples of the use cases. Use cases and policy recommendations should align and should have a solid basis.

Sebastian Gerbholz mentioned that IDERHA might think about how to position the project regarding the upcoming EHDS regulation. He emphasised that the reuse of existing resources and cooperations across existing research projects should be strengthened, as there is no need to re-invent the wheel. He encouraged the IDERHA project to explore involvement in the EHDS2 Board and pilot.

Conclusion

There are a wide range of key barriers and challenges to current data-sharing and access. These encompass attitudinal barriers such as a lack of altruism in data-sharing, governance barriers in the form of lack of harmonisation across international, national, and organisational policies, and more technical barriers such as interoperability. The most frequently cited challenges to data access and sharing were interoperability, uncertainty over legislation and governance, and the lack of a data-sharing culture or lack of trust to share data. Legislation/governance issues and interoperability were considered more sensitive to change through policy than attempting to enact culture change, however, the feasibility of addressing some of these challenges were unclear. Three of the barriers and challenges considered most impactful and feasible to address were incentivisation, patient/citizen consent, and increasing public spending on data-sharing and access. It will be important to consider the wider context of the EHDS and previous lessons learned when considering areas for policy development.

Recommendations

- IDERHA should explore policy recommendations for creating standardised incentives, promoting data altruism, and establishing clear governance procedures including appropriate consent mechanisms. This includes incentivising public and private entities to share data while ensuring transparent and ethical practices.
- IDERHA should assess the feasibility of implementing policy recommendations and seek to tackle areas where this is most likely. These recommendations should emphasise harmonisation at EU, national, and organizational levels.

Appendix 2 - Example of Miro board activity looking at feasibility and impact of addressing barriers

Appendix 3: Miro Board Results: perceived policy sensitivity of identified barriers and challenges

Barriers and challenges identified by participants listed in order they were placed on the scale of ‘can’t be influenced by policy change’ (indicated by red) to ‘can be influenced by policy change’ (indicated by green). Colour strength indicates proximity to the midline. Those in yellow indicate those placed on the midline between the two points.

Can't be influenced by policy change
Getting the actual decision maker to sign off sharing the data
Organisational/cultural barriers and differences
Lack of realism when defining project goals – not aligned to the data access situation “on the ground”
Long process for application process and finding/making access to data
Lack of data culture partnerships which requires a societal culture shift
Top barrier: lack of explained and explainable research
Resources needed to transform and make interoperable
Connectivity, interoperability standards
Interoperability
Everyone (researchers/clinicians) wants to access data. Nobody wants to share.
Lack of data-sharing infrastructure and platforms and challenges to international data flows

Consent by citizen, patient for primary, secondary usage of their data and continue to manage that consent granularity
Lack of incentive for data access providers
Citizens might distrust data-sharing platforms
Citizen's concerns for data-sharing (check latest TEHDAS outcome)
Standardisation of analyses definitions
Need to standardisation of clinical definitions across databases
Cloud solutions owned by third country
Limited intrinsic interoperability of many data sets "outside of the choir"
Data quality Data Bias
Health data governance model
Lack of or incomplete metadata or dataset catalogue
Collaboration with researchers can be helpful but where there is no example in a therapeutic area this can lead to a challenge in identifying what data it needs for the intended purpose
Which actors in the market can help to accelerate, esp. open approach and trans-border
Harmonisation, privacy and security and legal certainty
Consensus on definition of pseudonymised data and how these can be shared
Openness of data
Different interpretation of GDPR
Lack of trust (patient/citizen. Data holder, federations....)
Submitting data access applications where there is no clarity of what is needed and expected decisions - the going to and from can be time-consuming (SH)
Legal, Organisational semantic, Technical (usually the least problem?), Governance
Building trust
SeHa: Data availability
Limited quality/completeness of data sets
Align governance procedures
True data altruism
Expected timelines are short for procedures and processes to access data- standardised and accepted processes will help
Public funding = PPP for ramp up/readiness- extension of direct grants to MS for initial setup of NCP2/HDAB services, expansion of grants for initial implementation of MyHealth@EU eHDSI, offering secure processing environment as a service (esp. initially and for smaller countries)

Not everyone is equally incentivised to spend money and effort on the infrastructure
Legal uncertainties/unclarities
Harmonisation of EU acts - one big to come 'Reform of the EU pharmaceutical legislation' - common European goals of EU Health Union, Digital Society, along with harmonization of EU acts national implementations. EU Acts (AI Act, Data Act, Data Governance Act, revision of the EU general pharmaceuticals legislation) interrelate with multiple EU programs (Building resilience for future public health crisis / Rules on Cross Border Health Threats; OneHealth; ...
Different national legislation "on top of GDPR"
Can be influenced by policy change

Workshop Attendees

The data stakeholder workshop consisted of 10 participants that were/are involved in different projects aiming to facilitate data access, sharing and integration:

Name	Organisation	Relevant projects involved in
Professor Peter Rijnbeek	Erasmus University Medical Centre, Department of Medical Informatics	EHDEN, DARWIN
Niklas Hedberg	Dental and Pharmaceuticals Benefits Agency	EUnetHTA-21
Shahid Hanif	GetReal Institute	GetReal Institute
Rada Hussein	Ludwig-Boltzmann Institute	IDERHA
Erwin Dijkstra	Atos	Gaia-X
Sebastian Gerbholz	Atos	Gaia-X
Harald Wagener	Charité, Berlin Institute of Health	HEALTH-X dataLOFT
Christian Buggedei	Charité, Berlin Institute of Health	Gaia-X
Michel Silvestri	Head of Unit, Swedish eHealth Agency	TEHDAS
Elisabette Gatti	Johnson & Johnson	

The IDERHA members in attendance were:

Name	Organisation
Phillip Gribbon*	Fraunhofer Institute for Translational Medicine and Pharmacology
Lotte Gorth	DEFACTUM
Morten Deleuran Terkildsen	DEFACTUM
George Kolostoumpis	ECPC
Dipak Kalra	i-HD
Monica Brand	Johnson & Johnson
Heather Colvin	Johnson & Johnson
Ravinder Claire*	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence
Katharine Cresswell*	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence
Rebecca Lumsden*	Sanofi
Nataliya Kemenyash	Takeda

*Speaker

Appendix 5: Workshop agenda

Topic	Lead
Welcome and introductions	Ravinder Claire
IDERHA introduction	Phillip Gribbon
Audience Q&A	All
Miro board activity 1 – barriers and challenges	Katharine Cresswell

Miro board activity 2 – likely impact of policy change on barriers/challenges	Katharine Cresswell
Miro board activity 3 – Impact and feasibility of addressing barrier/challenge	Rebecca Lumsden
Closing question - advice for the project	Katharine Cresswell
Next steps	Katharine Cresswell

IDERHA Task 6.3 Data providers workshop 20/06/2024 - Full report

Introduction

On 20th June 2024, the IDERHA project held its fourth multi-stakeholder workshop. The online workshop gathered seven data protection officers, information governance officers and people working in associated roles from across healthcare sector organisations in Europe. The workshop aimed to hear the perspectives of stakeholders already engaged in the data-sharing and integration space, seeking to understand what IDERHA is best placed to deliver in terms of building policy recommendations for supporting data-sharing and integration. Specifically, the workshop aimed to:

- understand more about the challenges in assessing data access and sharing requests for research faced by those directly responsible for data protection in their role i.e. DPOs
- Understand both potential pragmatic and aspirational solutions to the challenges DPOs face, both now, in the mid-term (~next 5 years) and long-term after the implementation of proposed plans such as the European Health Data Space (EHDS).
- Understand possible nuances in challenges and solutions to data-sharing in different countries, organisation types (e.g. hospital vs. consultancy, for profit vs. not for profit)
- Get feedback from the DPOs on the proposed principals of the data management plan in IDERHA

Methodology

Data providers were identified from projects such as EHDEN, DARWIN, and HARMONY, from the HMA-EMA Catalogues of Real-world Data Sources¹ and also Biobanks and University Clinics. Both profit and not-for-profit healthcare data organisations were approached. We contacted the respective organizational contact person and/or DPO, if known, via e-mail, explained the aims of the workshop, and invited them to take part. Eight people confirmed their attendance, with one person withdrawing before the workshop took place. During the workshop, participants received an introduction to the IDERHA project. They were then asked to describe what they felt the role of a DPO/their role was within their organisation. This was followed by a discussion on the current barriers and challenges to health data-sharing and access, prompted using an image from the [EIT Health Think Tank report \(2024\): Implementing the European Health Data Space Across Europe](#) (Appendix 1). Participants were then asked to complete a polling question on their familiarity with the European Health Data

Space (EHDS), before being given a short overview of the EHDS and some of the key concepts that interplay with the existing General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Finally, an overview of the IDERHA Data Management Plan was provided.

To facilitate the discussion and for visualisation, Miro board was used (<https://miro.com>). Workshop participants were asked to identify their top barriers and challenges to data access and sharing and the potential solutions to these using virtual sticky notes.

The workshop agenda can be found in Appendix 2.

Role of a DPO/Information Governance Officer

It was felt that the focus of the role of DPO was on trying to support compliance with all relevant data protection laws, in particular GDPR, within the organisation. The challenges of doing this as an individual or a small team were acknowledged, as was the need to work and have support across the organization.

“The reality if you're a part of a big organisation...the idea of one person guaranteeing compliance is obviously impossible, but I can inform the policies, the procedures and also it takes a bit of a village... it'd be fair to say most people aren't doing this job solo”

It was noted that the acceptable decisions, processing actions and safeguards to be compliant is not always clear cut and so the DPO role is often to provide interpretation to the applicable privacy rules and regulations and then determine the most appropriate approach to take.

DPOs are expected to maintain their knowledge on all relevant legislations to be able to act as an ‘expert’ or adviser on such matters, ensuring organisational policies are kept up to date.

Additionally, the role involves raising awareness and conducting training among staff and stakeholders on relevant data protection regulations, compliance requirements and important updates to these.

Participant quotes on role of a DPO

“Act as the single contact point for supervisory authorities and DPOs at customer and vendor companies; oversee compliance with data subject requests; early involvement in DPIAs and privacy policy and procedures development, staying engaged with EU privacy forums and continuous GDPR training – basically "stay an expert" so when consulted on escalated privacy issues, I am able to determine the correct / most appropriate approach under GDPR / the applicable privacy rules and regs.”

“In my view, a DPO should ensure that an organization complies with data protection laws and regulations, particularly GDPR when dealing with data from the European Union. I see some

<p>basic roles and responsibilities for a DPO such as advising on policies and monitoring processes to ensure compliance.”</p>
<p>“Act as an advisor to the organisation on the protection of personal data it processes, including in relation to legal obligations under applicable data protection law, but also to operational and practical issues concerning protection of personal data.</p> <p>Overseeing data protection across the organisation, including risk assessments (DPIAs), and training and awareness.</p> <p>In reality, the role often involves acting as a ‘critical friend’ to the organisation, in terms of informing them of the data protection risks of proposed processing activities, while also recognising the benefits to the organisation’s strategic objectives.</p> <p>Acting as a senior, central point of contact for staff, customers, individuals, regulatory bodies and other stakeholders seeking to raise concerns. This also includes acting as an advocate for individuals who may not have a single voice, such as patients.”</p>
<p>“Provide advice, make sure to comply with different laws”</p>
<p>“My role is to guarantee GDPR compliance in the organisation by data process review and training and raising awareness among staff and stakeholders.”</p>
<p>Participants quotes on role of an information governance officer</p>
<p>“Establishing and overseeing processes for the safe and appropriate handling and sharing of personal and sensitive information relating to patients & health service users. Balancing the need to facilitate use while limiting the risks involved in management of data and ensuring regulator compliance. Key to this is engaging key stakeholders DPO/legal/public to build solutions!”</p>

Table 1. Participant quotes about purpose of DPO/their job role

Current barriers and challenges to access and sharing of data

The following barriers and challenges were identified and/or acknowledged by the participants:

Heterogenous interpretation of the GDPR – different organisations/countries will take different approaches based on their own perceptions of what is compliant

Lack of dedicated resources i.e. protected time, travel budget to engage within the network of DPOs to grow consensus on challenging topics contributes to differing interpretations

"So yes, there's certainly awesome networks. And again, it does come down to resource. You know, there ends up being lots of different sort of meetings we should be attending to and we can't"

"Individual Players following an unilateral maximum approach, thereby further enhancing the cross-sectoral and cross-jurisdictional gaps"

- **Legal basis fragmentation**
- **Determining the relevant legal basis e.g.** will consent be needed or will a different GDPR legal basis be more suitable?

"The GDPR itself is very principles based. It tells you what you must do. In order sets out the obligations, but it doesn't really tell you how to comply with them"

- **Concerns around anonymisation**
 - Ensuring anonymisation of health data and preventing indirect identification of patients, e.g. when linking the data with other data sources
 - Lack of standards on anonymization/ pseudonymization in research contexts
 - ♣ What these terms mean
 - ♣ Whether anonymised or pseudonymised data should be used

"Different institutions have different understanding of of what is Pseudonymous data or what is anonymized data. We have the same contract framework agreement...and there are a different interpretations of the same article for at least 50% of the of the different institutions, depending on the countries."

"Having to establish a lawful basis even to anonymise data is very tough when you can't rely on patient consent."

- **Transparency and trust on purpose of data use**
 - Understanding public value of use of data - to feed into risk balance assessment
 - Maintaining public trust in the appropriate use of health data e.g. the research must visibly be to benefit public health and/or patient care
 - How data would be used, i.e., no objection for research use by public data providers, however objection to the use from industry, or whether the results of research could have a commercial goal.

"there has been a barrier ... on who are how the data would be used, i.e., no objection for research use by public data providers. However, they would object to the use from industry, or whether the results of research could have a commercial goal."

- o Lack of transparency and visibility for patients
- **Disincentives for data-sharing**
 - o Lack of return (not necessarily economic, but information on data use, acknowledgement, reciprocity etc.) to the data provider
 - o Academic career incentives are often greater from not sharing data (publications, grant applications, reputation) may rely on not sharing primary data sources
 - o Industry concerns about trade secrets and commercial IP protection

"Academic career incentives from not sharing data!"

- **Technical barriers**
 - o Unstructured formats in Electronic Health Records (EHRs) means data not easily searchable and is therefore unused and some sources of EHR are not easily accessible e.g. primary care
 - o Unharmonised data models and data dictionaries
 - o Lack of interoperability of EHR and other health data systems

"..the way electrical records, which are something that is gonna be used more and more in Federated networks. They are so different even within the same country... They don't talk between them. So if you go from Spanish health record and try to compare it with the German one. It is totally impossible."

- **Cost and resource use**
 - o Maintaining accuracy EHRs costly / time-consuming
 - o The costs of data documentation and support of data-sharing (advising both potential users and organisations) cannot be covered by grants or core organisational funds

"The requirements to be a data a data provider are not very clear. And for some organisations, for big organisations it's OK, but for instance for non-profits like us. We are fearing that the requirements might require an investment that we cannot afford so that we don't have the resources."

- Knowledge gaps

- o Lack or trust due to lack of understanding of concepts and emerging technology

Introduction of the EHDS

Most participants rated their familiarity of the EHDS as 3 or below, (Table 2) when asked to rate from 1 to 5, where 1 was not at all familiar and 5 was very familiar. This lack of familiarity meant that most participants were unable to consider potential policy recommendations at this time, however, it was clear that there is concern that existing issues with heterogenous interpretation of the GDPR could be maintained or exacerbated with an additional set of legislation being added. It was stressed that getting the information and training on the different legislations, such as the EHDS was not the main concern, but rather the practical interpretation of different legislations in place and the question what legislation and law would apply under what scenarios. One participant mentioned the concern that especially small organisations might not be well be equipped for implementing the EHDS and for meeting the requirements a data provider would have to fulfil within the EHDS framework.

Participant No.	Rating
Participant 1	3
Participant 2	3-4
Participant 3	2
Participant 4	1-2
Participant 5	3
Participant 6	2

Table 2. Participant ratings on familiarity with EHDS where 1 was not at all familiar and 5 was very familiar.

Suggested solutions

Participants suggested a number of solutions to address the barriers that had been described:

- Harmonisation of GDPR interpretations for health data use
- Lobbying for reform of local laws governing health data processing, i.e. to allow processing to anonymise data without requiring patient consent (where public interest is not available, for example)
- Harmonising data models

- Data access via Secure Processing Environments/Trusted Research Environments, rather than traditional data-sharing models
- Use of synthetic data for AI/Machine Learning (BUT synthetic data may still be considered personal data under existing legal frameworks, so more specific regulation is likely to be required)
- Clarification of the practical requirements/risk mitigations for cross-border transfers where data are hosted in the EEA, but accessed from a third country
- 1-1 conversations between DPOs rather than forwarding information. Calls better than lengthy emails.

In addition, during the workshop a small number of IDERHA participants suggested the following solutions upon hearing the discussions:

- Approach as to data-sharing framework, based on efficiency risk mitigation (lose redundancy where possible)
- Cross-country agreements on the adequacy of information security safeguards for pseudonymised data
- Consensus on acceptable standards for adequate anonymisation, for different categories of data and scales of data sets
- Clarity on the granularity and specificity of broad consent that is still considered to be consistent with the GDPR

Conclusions and Recommendations

The greatest challenges facing DPOs and people working in associated roles are around ensuring correct interpretation of the legislation. There is a need to support and promote harmonisation of interpretation of the GDPR, and this will be even more important as new EHDS legislation comes into force.

Based on the discussions held in this workshop, the following recommendations could be made:

1. **Provide greater support in interpreting how best to comply with the GDPR, especially with regard to anonymisation**
2. **Ensure new EHDS legislation does not conflict with GDPR and clarify the interplay between EHDS and GDPR. Since EHDS will give rise to new scenarios requiring new GDPR interpretations, this would represent new challenges for the work of the DPOs. Provide training and support on EHDS for DPOs rather than just providing information to raise awareness of impacts on their job – this needs to be easily understandable, with relevant examples/case studies for their work and not burdensome as many DPOs and people in associated roles are already overstretched**
3. **Create opportunities for DPOs and people in associated roles to be able to connect to discuss problems and understand solutions others have taken.**

4. **Existing engagement opportunities should be promoted, since they are not well known or not widely used due to limited resources from the DPOs side. Hence, organizations should also provide resources (dedicated time and funding) for DPOs to take part in these opportunities.**

However, additional work is needed by IDERHA to further develop these recommendations to ensure effective implementation and impact:

- How/if should these recommendations be promoted by policy? There is an urgent need for policy makers to address these issues, but at the same time, policy makers work slowly and therefore may not be able to address every issue in time
- Who should be responsible for providing such support, training, opportunities?
- What level should these recommendations be targeted?
 - National
 - International
 - Organizations
 - Funders
 - DPOs

Appendix

Appendix 1 Current Data-sharing Barriers and Challenges Discussion Prompt

Image from: EIT Health Think Tank (2024): Implementing the European Health Data Space Across Europe

Appendix 2: Workshop agenda

Item	Timing
Welcome and introductions	10 mins (12.00-12.10)
Introduction to IDERHA	10 mins (12.10-12.20)
Role of a DPO	10 mins (12.20-12.30)
Key barriers & solutions – short to mid-term	35 mins (12.30-13.05)
Developing solutions – looking to the future (EHDS)	25 mins (13.05-13.30)
Developing solutions – IDERHA proposal	25 mins (13.30-13.55)
Next steps	5 mins (13.55 - 14.00)

IDERHA Task 6.3 and Task 6.2 Patient Organizations and Diversity and Inclusion Advocates Workshop 01/10/2024 - Full draft¹ report

Introduction

On 1st October 2024, the IDERHA project held its fifth multi-stakeholder workshop. The online workshop gathered 10 representatives from patient organisations, as well as diversity and inclusions advocates. The workshop was aimed at understanding patient and citizen perspectives on two key topics:

- Opt-out consent mechanisms for secondary data use
- Data breaches and misuse – particularly, how to rebuild trust after these occur

This workshop is the first in a series of workshops being undertaken to understand regional, ethical and societal concerns around appropriate data use for secondary health research. The aim of this task is to develop recommendations and build consensus on governance policies for accessing, sharing and using heterogenous data for research.

Methodology

Patient organization representatives and diversity and inclusion advocates were identified with support from IDERHA partner members, European Patient Forum and Lung Cancer Europe, and the IDERHA Patient Advisory Board. A shortlist of potential participants was created with the aim of maximizing representation of different health conditions, geographic areas of Europe, and minority or marginalized groups. Potential participants were contacted via e-mail to explain the aims of the workshop and invite them to take part. Twelve people confirmed their attendance and ten attended the online workshop. Attendees received some pre-read materials prior to the workshop to provide context, and to outline the questions that were covered in the workshop (Appendix 1).

Opt-out Consent Mechanisms

The workshop highlighted various nuanced perspectives on opt-out consent mechanisms. Participants discussed some advantages of opt-out vs opt-in systems such as, ease of application and practicality, and they also highlighted some concerns around opt-out systems, what would influence their decisions using them, as well as required information.

¹ As of the finalisation of this deliverable this workshop report was undergoing review by participants as described in the methodology section.

Participants stressed the need for clear definitions and descriptions of what constitutes health data as that is a determining factor on whether they would choose to opt-in or opt-out. For example, untraceable information such as age and gender, was easier to share than more specific information such as the name of their doctor and postcodes. Similarly, there were concerns raised about why it is important to capture aspects like ethnicity or sexual orientation in health data, as they can help with identifying potential health inequalities in research. However, there is also a risk of this data being used to identify people. As such appropriate stipulations and governance policies must be put in place to prevent participant identification and inappropriate use of the data. Appropriate monitoring and policies on who has access to the data can also help mitigate these concerns.

There were also concerns raised around equitable access and information sharing about opt-out mechanisms. Some participants highlighted that not all communities, for example people from lower socioeconomic backgrounds, would be aware of these schemes and as such may face barriers to exercising their rights. People with lower health literacy or people with disabilities who may require information on opting out in more accessible formats may also face barriers and issues with exercising their full rights. As such, if an opt-out system is implemented, it is important that it is accessible to all communities and sufficient information about the when/where/how the data will be used must be provided.

Furthermore, the participants highlighted that commercial use of their health data (i.e., for profit), as an area of concern and is often a deciding factor for some people. As the implications associated with commercial data use vary to the implications for data use in research. Participants highlighted that if data is used commercially, clear information on what the data is being used for and why it is being used, stipulations for opting out as well as compensation would be integral factors that would influence whether they would choose to provide their data for this use.

Quotes from participants:

What would influence your choice for opting out or not?

“Opt-out is practical, but without a clear definition of which data and who it will be used for – it could be problematic.”

“There could be problems with combining data and categorising, particularly for minority groups as it can reveal information about them.”

What information would you need to decide?

“We would need to know, who, what for, how? We would like to know and be involved from the beginning of the process – like a clinical study”

“How do you make sure you democratize the choice? The key is taking into account that research does not operate in the vacuum”.

“Do not forget that no research is possible if no healthcare data are provided”.

How would you like to be informed about the choices you have?

“Is the information in your native language? What if I am dyslexic? Blind? Is the information written in a way I can understand?”

“In as many forms as possible”

Data breaches and misuse

For this session in the workshop, participants were presented with two case studies and prompted to discuss their concerns about building and restoring trust following news reports of data breaches and data misuse, relating to an organisation they have previously permitted to use their health data, and in cases where the story regards an unrelated organisation. A key concern for participants was the long-term implications of data breaches, as they are seen to have potentially far-reaching and unpredictable consequences.

As such, participants emphasized that building trust after breaches requires significant efforts to rebuild trust with citizens. For example, participants highlighted the need for immediate notification about any data breaches/misuse, transparent communication about what caused the incident (e.g., human or system error) and clear investigation and mitigation approaches for both the data holder and data donor, to prevent incidents like this from happening again in the future.

Quotes from participants:

When you read about a data breach or data misuse in the news, to what extent does it make you nervous about how safe your own health data is, in your GP or hospital?

“If it was an accident, they would leave the data. However, if it was data misuse, I would like to know from the source what went wrong, rather than the news.”

“Research integrity and research ethics are needed for responsible research and a need to push the responsibility on researchers and how they use this secondary data.”

To what extent do these news stories affect how willing you are to consent that your health data can be used for research?

“Once data is out there, it's out there. If data breach occurs in a location that is far [from home/not locally] its less impactful, but the closer [the more local] the data breach is, the more of a problem it is.”

Does it affect you differently if the news stories are about health data or other data like financial (e.g. credit card data being exposed)?

“There is a difference between financial data and health data, as no health insurance company can recover health data as it can have real life consequences on personal security.”

“Have repercussions/severe consequences for entities who have data leaks, e.g. 5-year ban on data use, or a fine. Something that will have consequences on how they use data in the future”

If you think about the possibility of your health data being leaked or misused, what harms would you be most anxious about?

“‘Data that could be leaked’. If it was a private a provider, they wouldn’t use it again. But if it’s the national healthcare system, they would have no choice.”

If an organisation that holds your health data is hacked, what assurances and actions would you expect that organisation to take and inform you about, to rebuild your confidence?

“Besides the company telling me about the leak/misuse. I would like to be informed about possible consequences, and actions they could take to mitigate the risk for the misuse.”

Recommendations

Based on the discussions held in this workshop, the following recommendations could be made:

With regards to an opt-out option for secondary use of health data:

1. Provide an opt-out system that is user-friendly and inclusive, with clear communication strategies and clear definitions of what constitutes health data. This system should be targeted to all, especially minorities and those with lower data and health literacy levels.
2. Provide information about all potential purposes of secondary data use, stakeholders involved, and data types, while also acknowledging that this might be challenging in practice.

3. Communicate all potential benefits, risks, and consequences (both positive and negative) of opting out, so that people can make informed choices.
4. Actively engage with citizens from diverse backgrounds, including those that have or continue to face persecution, to thoughtfully address potential concerns with regards to the political and social contexts of secondary use of health data.
5. Acknowledge that emotional and not only rational factors play a role in opt-out decisions.
6. Reassure individuals who have opted out that their data is not being used for secondary purposes.
7. Consider the reasons behind opt-out decisions for drawing accurate conclusions from datasets used for secondary purposes.

With regards to responding to data breaches and building trust with citizens:

1. Share information as soon as a breach is discovered, even if it is still not certain what exactly happened. It is better for patients/citizens to learn about a breach from the organisation rather than to hear about it first in the news.
2. Share information directly with patients/citizens if their data has been part of a breach, informing them of what data has been breached and if anything is known about the risks.
3. Share information about how the breach happened and if the data has already been misused in connection with the breach.
4. Share information on what the organisation/company will do to handle the consequences of a data breach including risk mitigation and future prevention. Offer to follow up when new information arises. This applies both after a data breach and when data is handed over for legitimate use.

Appendix 1: Pre-read material

Figure 1: Overview of health data

What is Anonymization and Pseudonymisation?

Anonymous data is data that cannot be linked to a specific person and hence the person cannot be identified from the data. When figuring out whether a person cannot be identified from the data, all the possible methods should be considered, including how much time and effort it takes to identify the person and what technology is available at the time of data processing.

Pseudonymisation is the process of making personal data unidentifiable to a specific person by replacing the identifying information (e.g. the name) with a random code. However, the data can still be connected to a person with a key, i.e. extra information (e.g. an allocation list). This extra information must be kept separate from the identifiable data to prevent unauthorized people from accessing the data.

Figure 2: What is anonymization and pseudonymisation

What is primary use of health data?

Figure 3: What is primary use of health data?

Figure 4: What is secondary use of health data?

What is “opt-out” for secondary use of data?

Figure 5: What is “opt-out” for secondary use of data?

First session

During the workshop we will discuss the following questions in the first session. Please could you think about these in advance, so you can contribute well to our discussions.

- What do you think about the opt-out system?
- What would influence your choice for opting out or not? What information would you need to decide?
- How would you like to be informed about your choices?
- How do you feel about the possibility that the opt-out could be overruled by public bodies in case of public interest?

Second session

Patients need to trust that their health data will be securely protected and used only for agreed purposes in research. However, frequent news stories about data breaches, including some involving health data, can undermine this trust. We aim to explore how these reports impact your willingness to allow your data to be used for research.

Definitions

A data leak of personal data is when data about individuals is accidentally unprotected or criminally accessed through hacking, exposing that personal data to unauthorised people who may use it for malicious purposes, e.g. a spreadsheet containing personal details sent by email.

Data misuse is when an organisation is authorised to have personal data for some agreed purposes but chooses deliberately to use it for another purpose that might not have been agreed, e.g. data collected from patients for a research project, with patient consent, being used for marketing purposes.

Second session: Case 1

Health data breach: Dedalus Biologie fined 1.5 million euros

4 May 2022 [France](#)

Background information

Date of final decision: 15 April 2022

Cross-border case or national case: National case

Controller: DEDALUS BIOLOGIE

Legal Reference: Processing under the authority of the controller or processor (Article 29 GDPR), Security of processing (Article 32 GDPR), Processor (Article 28 GDPR)

Decision: Administrative fine

Key words: Health data breach

Summary of the Decision

Origin of the case

On February 23, 2021, a massive data breach regarding nearly 500,000 people was revealed in the press, involving the company Dedalus Biologie. The name, first name, social security number, name of the prescribing doctor, date of the examination, but also and above all medical information (HIV, cancers, genetic diseases, pregnancies, drug therapy of patients, or genetic data) of these people were thus released on the Internet.

Second session: Case 2

Royal Free breached UK data law in 1.6m patient deal with Google's DeepMind

[Alex Hern](#)

Photograph: Alamy Stock Photo

London's Royal Free hospital failed to comply with the Data Protection Act when it handed over personal data of 1.6 million patients to [DeepMind](#), a Google subsidiary, according to the Information Commissioner's Office.

The data transfer was part of the two organisation's partnership to create the healthcare app Streams, an alert, diagnosis and detection system for acute kidney injury.

Patients were not adequately informed that their data would be used as part of the test.

"A patient presenting at accident and emergency within the last five years to receive treatment or a person who engages with radiology services and who has had little or no prior engagement with the Trust would not reasonably expect their data to be accessible to a third party for the testing of a new mobile application, however positive the aims of that application may be"

During the workshop we will discuss the following questions in the second session. Please could you think about these in advance, so you can contribute well to our discussions.

1. When you read about a data breach or data misuse in the news, to what extent does it make you nervous about how safe your own health data is, in your GP or hospital?
2. To what extent do these news stories affect how willing you are to consent that your health data can be used for research?
3. Does it affect you differently if the news stories are about health data or other data like financial (e.g. credit card data being exposed)
4. If you think about the possibility of your health data being leaked or misused, what harms would you be most anxious about?

5. If an organisation that holds your health data is hacked, what assurances and actions would you expect that organisation to take and inform you about, to rebuild your confidence?

Appendix 2: Workshop Agenda

Time (CEST)	Topic	Moderator
16.30 -16.45	Welcome, group exercise, and introduction to IDERHA	Katharine Cresswell
16.45 - 17.30	Session 1: Opt-out – examples and discussion	Nadja Kartschmit
17.30 - 17.40	Short break	
17.40 - 18.25	Session 2: Data breach and misuse – examples and discussion	Dipak Kalra
18.25-18.30	Wrap-up and next steps	Lotte Groth Jensen

